

Flight, Food & Flavor: The Impact of Quality Cuisine During in-Flight Catering on Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines

A Research Study

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

COVER PAGE.....	1838
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	1839
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	1840
ABSTRACT	1841
INTRODUCTION	1842
<i>A. Background of the Study</i>	1842
<i>B. Theoretical Framework</i>	1843
<i>C. Conceptual Framework</i>	1843
<i>D. Statement of the Problem</i>	1844
<i>E. Significance of the Study.....</i>	1844
<i>F. Review of Related Literature</i>	1844
I. METHODOLOGY.....	1846
<i>A. Research Design</i>	1846
<i>B. Informants</i>	1846
<i>C. Settings</i>	1846
<i>D. Instrumentation.....</i>	1846
<i>E. Data Analysis.....</i>	1846
<i>F. Ethical Considerations</i>	1846
II. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS	1847
III.DISCUSSION.....	1853
<i>A. Conclusions</i>	1853
<i>B. Recommendations</i>	1853
References.....	1854
APPENDIX	1856

ABSTRACT

In the world of civil aviation where airline choices are verily abundant, there are multiple factors that passengers take into consideration when making a final decision such as price, routes, convenience, and even the food they serve on board. Putting emphasis on the last factor, this study entitled “Flight, Food & Flavor: The Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-Flight Catering on Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines” aims to identify the role that food plays in the perception and air travel experience of passengers, particularly with how the various elements of a quality cuisine service affects the overall flight experience of a passenger and whether or not it's an airline deal breaker for them. In order to achieve this goal, the researchers gathered the necessary data via interviewing informants who experienced quality cuisine as part of the service provisions their airline provided within the confines of economy class, with regards to their first-hand accounts and experiences in the respective legacy airlines they have flown. The results of this study will allow the researchers to provide a basis of standard for which airlines can discern the expectations and perceptions of passengers in economy class and adjust or improve their meal services to better accommodate them, as well as attract and pander to a larger audience of customers.

Keywords:- Quality Cuisine, Economy Class, Passengers, Satisfaction, Perception, Cultural Appropriateness, In-flight Catering, International, Legacy/Full-Service Airlines.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

For as long as legacy airlines have operated, high-quality in-flight meal service remains a staple and an expected commodity of increasing demand. As such, airlines that provide full services are required to have exceptional food and beverage services for the airline industry is a highly competitive market. Be that as it may, catering services in legacy airlines vary and even took quite a bit of a downturn. The rise of deregulation and terrorist attacks were the main culprits in the decline of food quality and service within the airline industry. While food quality certainly decreased during the deregulation era, legacy airlines made an effort in maintaining and modernizing their food service and quality as well as making them sustainable and eco-friendly via innovative means.

Such innovative means translate to technological innovations and expert culinary intervention that have provided airlines with an improved array of quality food products than their previous portfolios. Additionally, the advancements made in storing food ensure that the containers are eco-friendly and that the condition of the food would not deteriorate whilst in-flight. These developments showcase the dedication and innovation already being implemented to enable airlines to provide high-quality meal services without sacrificing ethical integrity. Although in-flight taste buds are affected by a variety of factors, airlines may adjust their food quality accordingly in order to better suit their passengers' palates. With regards to foodborne illnesses, specialist organizations devote themselves unto the task of assessing the quality of food products and ingredients ensuring that they delivered properly and clear for safety concerns.

Considering all this, the importance of food services in airlines is highlighted by the customers themselves. Since plenty of flights occur internationally, available food and wide- ranging services are preferred during the length of time in their flights. Moreover, passengers typically choose airlines that provide the best in-flight meals which corresponds with food quality being a major factor in customers satisfaction. This shows the correlation between great service and food quality with customer satisfaction as well as customer retention and as such, a focus on this department should be implemented in legacy airlines. In addition, this also proves the interdependency between the quality of food attributes and customer satisfaction and loyalty. Hence why legacy airlines must put an emphasis on food quality is to improve their overall cabin crew services.

A. *Background of the Study*

The airline industry has long been driven by competition, with airlines constantly trying to achieve a competitive edge over the other. Before the Airline Deregulation Act of 1978 was signed, airlines were controlled by the government entities such as the Civil Aeronautics Board, which handled the procurement of standardized fares and routes. This means that all airlines must adhere to the same flight prices depending on the specific flight route. Due to this, airlines were forced to compete via in-flight services to create a competitive advantage and differentiate themselves from their contemporaries. Airlines started by providing passengers with high-end restaurant-quality meals that are served on dining plates along with metallic utensils. Culinary competency dictated the competition between these legacy airlines, and whoever provided the best meals usually were also associated with having the best service. However, this all came to an end when the Airline Deregulation Act of 1978 was signed and passed by former President Jimmy Carter (González J., 2022). This allowed the liberalization of fares and routes so that airlines could finally change their flight ticket prices independently. As such, many airlines dropped high-quality meals and other flight services in favor of lower prices that can fit in anyone's budget regardless of class. Furthermore, although many airlines still provide in-flight catering, the reduction of focus on food has led to less mediocre food quality that is only exacerbated by the difference of taste in altitude. In some cases, such food products have even resulted in food poisoning during flight.

Despite low-cost carriers compromising food for lower prices, legacy carriers who had continuously provided fully-fledged services have initiated increasing quality of service to maximize the ticket price that passengers pay more for in legacy carriers. One of these services is the provision of quality meals and catering services. Since the decline of catering services within the airline industry, many legacy airlines have decided to increase the entirety of their services as a competitive advantage over low-cost carriers (Aviation Business News, 2019b). Although the public has always downgraded the quality of food within the airline industry, legacy carriers' swift change to improve their services has been seen with great success. Legacy airlines such as Emirates and Singapore Airlines utilizing technological advancements in food creation and preparation have propelled their airlines with having the best food onboard (Carl, 2023). They typically serve a variety of cuisines that are based on either their own country of origin or other countries depending on the flight's destination. The variety of cuisine served on these international flights has greatly amplified the cultural diversity and delivery to the flying public. Overall, the purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of in-flight catering services with customer preference and perception as well as signify the importance of in-flight catering towards both customers and airlines alike.

B. Theoretical Framework

Fig 1: The Gaps Model of Service Quality by Zeithaml & Bitner (1996)

In conjunction with the study of the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-Flight Catering on Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines, the gaps model of service quality by Zeithaml & Bitner (1996) is optimal considering the fact that quality cuisine is an integral part of in-flight services. The gaps model functions as a framework for which factors regarding service quality are interconnected to identify discrepancies between the relationships of these factors (gaps) and tweak accordingly to achieve improved service quality. The researchers aim to relate quality cuisine with the factors in the gaps model according to expectation, perception, and satisfaction to identify variables involved in the correlation between quality cuisine and customer perception.

C. Conceptual Framework

Fig 2: The Relationship Between Customer's Perception and Satisfaction

The framework for this study is based upon the correlation between the relationship of perception with the basis of expectation and the satisfaction of individuals. This separates the factors of consumer interaction that can cause different perceptions and expectations of the delivery of in-flight catering services. The factors are divided into five variables revolving around customer expectation, choice, delivery and design, satisfaction, and perception. These are variables that are dependent on one another for a process and relationships to be identified.

Under the gaps model of service quality (Zeithaml & Bitner, 1996), each variable is interconnected to each other. Each relationship between the variables has a subsequent impact on the other variables which can cause a difference in the outcome. All of the variables concentrate on the end line of customer perception that can cause further different outcomes in choice, expectation, delivery, and satisfaction to consumers in a cycle. The gaps model is used to identify any factors within that can be narrowed down to improve upon any shortcomings that can lead to a change in any of the variables when it comes to consumer perception of the in-flight catering service that can influence the customer's choice.

D. Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to analyze the correlation between the provision of quality cuisine and customer satisfaction and perception. Additionally, ascertain whether the impact of quality cuisine affects customer selection in terms of airlines. As such, the study intends to answer the following questions:

- What is the effect of quality cuisine on customer preference?
- How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection?
- How is cultural appropriateness and presentation relevant to the customer's perception of quality?

E. Significance of the Study

The research examines the impacts of high-quality cuisine in inflight meals provided by airline companies, focusing on a vital component of the passenger air travel experience. The findings of this research would benefit not only the researchers and the aviation industry but also a wide variety of stakeholders, including airline companies, passengers, economies, and catering companies. Specifically, this study's results would benefit the following groups:

- Produce Suppliers. The research intends to provide the benefits of food storage and preparation, encouraging suppliers to innovate and collaborate with the aviation industry to deliver pristine in-flight dining experiences.
- Catering Companies. The study focuses on the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-Flight Catering so that they can expand their knowledge regarding enhancing the customer's overall experience and satisfaction. This plays an important role in the success and image of the catering company in the selection of airlines for catering services.
- Passengers. Foods served to the customers take part in maintaining the quality standards of an airline. Researchers aim to provide knowledge on what customers should expect from the food being served during the flight.
- Future Airlines. The research shows the behavior of customers which suggests that airlines investing in quality in-flight catering could increase their income and customer satisfaction. This will contribute to positive financial growth, popularity, and the stability of full-service airlines.
- In-Flight Cabin Services. The service that the passengers will receive from the flight crew is a very important aspect of in-flight catering that reduces food contamination and focuses on the efficiency of provision. As this study suggests, with the increase of significance in food catering, cabin crew will be better trained and informed in the proper standards of in-flight service.
- Future Researchers. This research can provide the necessary information to fund the foundation in which future researchers would construct based on the topic of quality cuisine in in-flight catering. These future studies may expound on the topic at hand as well as all the affecting factors.
- The study aims to show the significance of how the cuisines served by each airline greatly affect the entire business. It could help not only the company, faculty, and students but future researchers as well. Understanding this could enhance their knowledge and know what works and what doesn't work in the field of aviation.

F. Review of Related Literature

Based on (Gamal, H. E., 2021), service quality is a key to attract and keep loyal customers (Chang and Yeh, 2002; Gursoy et al., 2005; Liou and Tzang, 2007). On-board food is an important dimension of airline services. In particular, Solomon (2002) noted that passengers generally will choose the airline that offers the best food. Further, on-board food services now are seen as part of marketing strategies in attracting all kinds of travelers (Jones, 1995). In this regard, King (2001) reported that some passengers would be willing to change airlines, alter travel patterns and even pay more money for the high quality of on-board food served.

In-flight meal satisfaction was found to significantly contribute to the prediction of passengers' flight satisfaction and loyalty, especially meal taste, preferences, and service. The strength and significance of this prediction varied according to flight details and passengers' travel habits and individual characteristics; such as the airline company, seat class, route, trip purpose, flight duration, flying experience in general and with the airline, travel party, and passengers' socio-demographics. (Al Balushi, H. J. G. 2020)

There are significant differences between flight distance and preferred foods, nutrition dimension, sanitation dimension, menu, supplementary service dimension, employee dimension. Importance of dimensions rises together with the longer flight distances (Sariođlan, M., 2018).

In other words, in-flight food and beverage quality is becoming essential for airlines in the effort to attract customers and outperform airline competitors. In the highly competitive airline industry, satisfying existing and potential passengers should be the priority of a full-service airline business that aims to stimulate repeat purchases (Han et al., 2019).

The empirical results and findings suggest that there is a significant impact of service quality on passenger satisfaction and loyalty in the Indian aviation industry. The result further shows that empathy and responsiveness are the prominent factors of service quality which is a vital prerequisite for customer satisfaction (Walia et al., 2021).

Based on (Hwang, E.; Kim, Y.-S.; Song, H.G. 2023), well-designed inflight food service highly correlates with overall service quality and satisfaction for business and economy-class travelers (Park, J.W. 2007). These airline passengers presented the highest perceived value for onboard meal service (Chen, C.F.; Wu, T.F. 2009).

Designing an in-flight meal is a work of art. The menu not only needs to cater to a diverse range of tastes and dietary preferences but also consider the challenges of serving food at high altitudes. Airlines collaborate with expert chefs and nutritionists to create menus that are not only delicious but also nutritionally balanced. From tantalizing appetizers to delectable desserts, every dish is meticulously chosen to ensure passenger satisfaction (Team, L. (2023b, December 20). *Airplane Food: Behind the scenes of In-Flight catering. How to Make a Paper Airplane*).

Economy Class passengers are also treated to satisfying meals that cater to diverse tastes. These guests can select from international dishes like Chinese, Indian Subcontinent, or vegetarian meals, depending on their preferences. Emirates ensures dietary requirements for passengers with special needs like gluten-friendly, low lactose, or medically necessary dietary restrictions, are met [Carl. (2023, November 23). *Do Emirates provide food: In-flight dining options explained. Travel Spock*].

Another type of culture is medical diets, including low/high fiber, low fat/cholesterol, diabetic, peanut-free, non-lactose, low salt/sodium, low-purine, low-calorie, low-protein, and gluten-free meals. Religious diets, including kosher food, Hindu, Buddhist, and halal food, and Asian vegetarian meals. Some airlines do not offer a specific meal for non-vegan vegetarians; instead, they are given a vegan meal (Gunardi, Ariawan, & Martono, K. (2018, June 26). *Airlines Meals Service: LEGAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS. UGC Approved Journal*).

CHAPTER TWO METHODOLOGY

A. *Research Design*

The researchers intend to identify the impact of quality cuisine on customer "perception," necessitating a qualitative research design. This approach involves gathering data through observation, interviews, focus groups, and participant narratives of their firsthand experiences. By employing qualitative methods, the researchers seek to develop hypotheses that offer a comprehensive understanding of the nuances and implications derived from the findings. This study explores how perceptions are shaped by the quality of cuisine, providing valuable insights into consumer behavior and preferences in culinary contexts.

B. *Informants*

The study focuses on frequent flyers within the flying public, specifically those who regularly use full-service carriers such as Philippine Airlines, Cathay Pacific, and All Nippon Airways, particularly on economy class for international flights. The informants will be individuals associated with an aeronautical aviation school near Parañaque City, encompassing students, faculty, and staff. A targeted sample size of six (6) informants is deemed adequate for gathering comprehensive data pertinent to the study's objectives. This approach ensures that insights gathered reflect the experiences and perspectives of informed individuals within the aviation community, thereby enriching the thesis with relevant and specialized knowledge.

C. *Settings*

The researchers conducted this study at an aeronautical aviation school situated on Lombos street, San Isidro, Parañaque City, during the Midyear Class of the Academic Year 2023 to 2024. The institution's robust aviation programs made it an ideal setting for this research, leveraging its esteemed reputation in the field. The study was conducted within the campus premises, utilizing designated areas including lecture halls and conference rooms, which offered a conducive environment for gathering qualitative data.

D. *Instrumentation*

The primary method for data collection will involve conducting face-to-face interviews with selected informants within the campus of an aeronautical aviation school. These informants include students, working professionals, and staff. Each interview will consist of a structured set of seven (7) questions designed to explore passenger experiences, perceptions, and satisfaction levels, specifically focusing on the influence of food quality on inflight experiences. This approach aims to gather valuable feedback for enhancing services based on customer comments and suggestions.

E. *Data Analysis*

To gather data for this study, the researchers conducted face-to-face interviews at any vacant room within PATTS College of Aeronautics granted the said room is enclosed and free from the public. The researchers recorded precise, accurate information and annotated the transcripts by the informants' responses. In line with this, a thematic analysis was considered upon analyzing the data to conduct a respective occurrence that will develop concepts throughout the study.

Thematic analysis is one of the few ways to analyze qualitative data. Usually, it is used in relation to a collection of texts, such as transcripts or interviews which is highly applicable to this study. To find recurring themes such as topics, concepts, and patterns of meaning, the researcher carefully scrutinized the data in a table form and divided it into two categories: master themes and superordinate themes.

F. *Ethical Considerations*

This study ensures the responsible handling of all informant-provided information, strictly adhering to privacy and confidentiality standards. Measures will be implemented to ensure compliance with relevant rules and regulations. Transparency will be maintained throughout the research process, emphasizing informed consent with informants and clearly outlining the security measures in place to protect their information. Furthermore, transcripts from interviews will be used for data analysis, with strict protocols in place to safeguard the confidentiality of each informant's identity and responses.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Results

This study revolves around a sample of six (6) informants who had been interviewed regarding their food experiences aboard international flights via legacy airliners in economy class. This research aims to analyze the connection between quality cuisine and customer perception. As such, each interview per informant is crucial in the process of completing the said objective. In essence, the results of each interview would be analyzed and evaluated with regard to the influence of quality cuisine on the informants’ opinions, perceptions, satisfaction, and airline loyalty/selection.

B. Based on the Data Gathered from the Informants, what is the Effect of Quality Cuisine on Customer Preference?

Table 1: Master Themes Based on the Data Gathered from the Informants, what is the Effect of Quality Cuisine on Customer Preference

Master Themes	Superordinate Themes
Passengers generally have a notion that legacy airlines will include in-flight meals on international flights.	Complementary
Good quality in-flight cuisine elevates the experience of customers.	Enhance
The quality of inflight food has an effect on the customer.	Satisfaction

- Master Theme 1: Passengers generally have a notion that legacy airlines will include in-flight meals on international flights.
- Superordinate Theme 1.1: Complementary
- Informant 1: “We expect them (Legacy Airlines) to serve food... especially on long-haul flights.”
- Informant 6: “While you’re stuck in the air, you’re left with only, ... of course the food.”

The serving of in-flight food is welcomed in terms of customer service offered by a legacy airline. A notion is made where having complementary food from a legacy airline has become commonplace and is an expected within flight service. Providing in-flight on international flights is a part of the experience when flying with legacy airlines.

- Master Theme 2: Good quality in-flight cuisine elevates the experience of customers.
- Superordinate Theme 1.2: Enhance
- Informant 1: “It makes... sitting down for like more than ten hours bearable.”
- Informant 2: “*Mas enjoyable... especially when kapag mainit na yung ulo... if delayed yung flight.*”
- Informant 3: “It makes my experience way better.”
- Informant 5: “f the food is good, the experience is great for the passengers.”
- Informant 6: “I’d like really good food, appetizing... good to look at.”

Providing in-flight meal is a morale boosting part of flight. At this point, having an in-flight meal is no longer just to supplement the service, but also making a better experience. On top of it, food has a factor that can change the mood of individuals with it not just nourishing the body, but also the mental state of the passengers. Thus, the majority of the informants agreed that in-flight cuisine creates a more enhanced flight experience.

- Master Theme 3: The quality of in-flight food has an effect on the customer.
- Superordinate Theme 1.3: Satisfaction
- Informant 1: "... did not serve, it wasn't stated and it's pretty disappointing."
- Informant 3: "if we eat food we would be happy and... not angry all the time."
- Informant 4: "Good food is happiness and if you're happy, then you're satisfied."

Satisfaction of the consumer can be highly influenced by the in-flight service that they received, which includes serving of food. The quality of food being served has an impact on how customers feel about the cuisine being served to them. Having food not just being offered to them can greatly affect a customers' satisfaction; having good food means being satisfied as stated by one of the informants. In such cases where quality of food or even the serving of in-flight cuisine is lacking or altogether not being offered, it will lead to a significant negative impact on the customer's satisfaction.

C. Based on the Data Gathered from the Informants, how will the Provision of Quality Cuisine Affect Customer Airline Selection?

Table 2: Master Themes based on the Data Gathered from the Informants, how will the Provision of Quality Cuisine Affect Customer Airline Selection

Master Themes	Superordinate Themes
It is favorable to have food included in the booking of the ticket.	Convenience
Having remarkable or quality food in-flight can improve an airline's image.	Reputation
Socio-economic status has a factor in selecting an airline.	Income

- Master Theme 1: It is favorable to have food included in the booking of the ticket.
- Superordinate Theme 1.1: Convenience
- Informant 1: "We assume that the food is already included... so we just look into the ticket price."
- Informant 2: "*Hindi mo na kailangan maglabas ng money...*"
- Informant 4: "It's highly favorable for me... I don't need to... buy food at the terminals."

The inclusion of food while booking a ticket is not only received positively by the informants, but also expected by them. This is due to the fact that expectations towards legacy airlines are on a higher level, as well as the price hike typically seen in legacy airline tickets. Additionally, with the food already included with the ticket, informants perceived this as convenient to them since they no longer have to purchase food within the terminal or in-flight.

- Master Theme 2: Having remarkable or quality food in-flight can improve an airline's image.
- Superordinate Theme 1.2: Reputation
- Informant 1: "Shows how much they care for passenger experience."
- Informant 4: "People review a lot... They read reviews as well so it will be affecting."
- Informant 5: "I would not only fly with them again, but I would also recommend."
- Informant 6: "If the food is really good, I would not only fly... also recommend it to my friends."

The provision of quality cuisine has a massive impact whether positive or negative towards customer experience and satisfaction. Customers who are satisfied with the quality of food will inherently have a desire to fly again with that airline. As such, the reputation of said airline would skyrocket by means of recommendations through word-of-mouth. However, on the contrary, negative reviews based on quality cuisine would result in a negative reputation for that specific legacy airline.

- Master Theme 3: Socio-economic status is a factor in selecting an airline.
- Superordinate Theme 1.3: Income
- Informant 1: “Ticket price and the availability.”
- Informant 3: “Many factors as like you know financial.”
- Informant 4: “Comfortability or happiness is expensive... worth the price.”

Based on the informants’ statements, their socioeconomic status plays a role in determining whether quality cuisine is enough to urge them to buy a more expensive ticket for a more comfortable experience. In these cases, the most prevalent factor is their financial stability. Customers who can pay for a better experience would gladly do so, while others who are short on money may compromise their comfort for a more budget-friendly flight. With that said, if allowed to acquire both ticket price and availability within their favor, quality cuisine would be one of the priorities along with comfortability.

D. Based on the Data Gathered from the Informants, how are Cultural Appropriateness and Presentation Relevant to the Customer’s Perception of Quality?

Table 3: Master Themes based on the Data Gathered from the Informants, how is Cultural Appropriateness and Presentation Relevant to the Customer’s Perception of Quality

Master Themes	Superordinate Themes
Having more than one option of in-flight meals has a positive effect on the customer.	Variety
Having in-flight cuisine influenced by the airline's nationality and destination can provide a uniqueness.	Distinction
In-flight meals should take into account dietary needs in terms of culture and religion.	Consideration
Presentation of in-flight cuisine is a factor to customers' perception.	Impression

- Master Theme 1: Having more than one option of in-flight meals has a positive effect on the customer.
- Superordinate Theme 1.1: Variety
- Informant 3: “I’m satisfied to know that there’s a lot of variety.”
- Informant 4: “Of course there’s a lot of options and a lot of variety... as well as different types.”
- Informant 5: “I’d say the quality matters most than the variety.”
- Informant 6: “*Sa economy kasi* you don’t have any options.”

Having the option to choose is a privilege that people would always like to have. Having choice means having freedom and in turn would make a customer’s experience more akin to the preference. The informants expressed their liking to have variety and options to their choice of in-flight cuisine being offered by a legacy airline, breaking the monotony of having the same meal over again. Added to this is that the choice is brought not by the desire, but the necessity due to dietary or cultural restrictions. Yet in some cases, economy class customers of legacy airlines do not have this privilege. In line with this, one informant stated that less can sometimes be better with quality having a greater factor rather than multiple options and variety.

- Master Theme 2: Having more than one option of in-flight meals has a positive effect on the customer.
- Superordinate Theme 1.2: Distinction
- Informant 2: “Airlines cater to diverse food culture tastes.”
- Informant 3: “Sometimes they give their own spin... they give their own arabic bread like that which is nice.”
- Informant 4: “You have the choice... (to) taste their culture before actually getting to that place.”

- Informant 5: “Try their culture.”
- Informant 6: “... route, *iba-iba sila ng cuisine kasi iba-iba din* and food selection”

Commonly, legacy airlines are national carriers for their respective nations. That is why they must present who and what they are to their customers. Distinction is a vital factor to how an airline can attract and retain their customers. Cuisine is a good vehicle to express this with cuisine of culture being distinct to one another. An airline can provide, as one informant stated, a spin or version of a cuisine. Supplementing this, having food of their destination can help improve the experience of the customers by giving a taste of what they may have when they land.

- Master Theme 3: In-flight meals should take into account dietary needs in terms of culture and religion.
- Superordinate Theme 1.3: Consideration
- Informant 1: “You have options to alter... If you have dietary restrictions.”
- Informant 2: “Airlines cater to... dietary needs.”
- Informant 3: “Vegetarian or like those with diets *na* they can't really consume like those... that's accommodating.”
- Informant 4: “I'm a Muslim it's much better because they provided halal options.”
- Informant 6: “Food is important to me... I'm hypoglycemic so I have to have food.”

Cultural and religious beliefs have an influence in customer preferences especially when it comes to cuisine. Be that as it may, informants have stated that airlines do provide customers with options that adhere to their culinary preferences and dietary limitations. For instance, vegetarian customers have options for vegetarian meals and Muslims have options for halal meals. Furthermore, customers who require specific dietary needs also have options provided by the airline. This shows that regardless of cultural and religious background, all customers in-flight would be able to enjoy their preferred meals.

- Master Theme 4: Presentation of in-flight cuisine is a factor to customers' perception.
- Superordinate Theme 1.4: Perception
- Informant 1: “Type of food they serve can affect my perception of them.”
- Informant 2: “As a *foodie syempre*, I'll take a picture *ganun*.”
- Informant 3: “*Sinerve siya naka paper cup lang*.”

As much as quality cuisine impacts customer satisfaction, the actual presentation of food towards the customer also highlights an important aspect of proper culinary provisions in-flight. Despite that, informants' perception on presentation is a mixed bag. Some informants specify that the presentation of food has an effect of perception towards them. They also specify that food photos are as important to them as quality of food. However, considering that economy class isn't necessarily known for their presentation, some informants state that presentation has no hold on their own perception.

E. Findings

➤ Statement of the Problem 1: Quality Food and Preference

- The in-flight catering of quality cuisine is a very important part when it comes to international flight stated by the informants, particularly if the flight is long-haul where the serving of in-flight meals is a welcomed addition to the flight and therefore crucial to the experience itself. Added to this the notion that legacy airlines would provide in-flight cuisine as complementary is a factor for their experience as a whole.

- The informants stated that having in-flight food offers a better experience, providing a good flight experience through the provision of the food itself being part of the experience by giving a morale booster to them enhancing the flight experience with the said airline.
- The uplifting effect of good quality cuisine in-flight has incentives wherein during flight it is elevating the experience of providing food that is tasty and makes the passengers feel satisfied with their choice. This satisfaction of the product being offered by the legacy airline would greatly affect their stance within the relationship between business and customer.

➤ *Statement of the Problem 2: Customers' Selection.*

- In-flight quality cuisine has been shown to greatly influence the likelihood of purchasing an airline ticket. As such, airlines that provide quality catering services as part of their ticket is proven to be appealing towards customers and seems to attract more customers via word of mouth. This in turn allows customers to develop their loyalty towards the airline due to the irresistible enticement given by the food itself.
- The student informants typically focus on ticket price and availability. With that said, some passengers, such as the professional informants, prefer flight experience rather than price which leads to them purchasing a more expensive ticket to accommodate comfort and quality cuisine.
- Nevertheless, both the student and professional informants have proven that quality food is still a major factor when it comes to airline selection. Additionally, the variety of food and the fact that passengers are given a choice towards their preferred meals have led to great satisfaction.
- On the contrary, if passengers receive cuisine that is not up to their standards, their tolerance for the airline is short-lived and customer loyalty would be shattered. Furthermore, if the passenger feels like the food is getting repetitive, this also forces them to change airlines.

➤ *Statement of the Problem 3: Factor of Variety, Culture, and Presentation*

- The variety of quality food has proven to be quite a welcome service detail with regards to the provisioned meals of the airlines and generally speaking, having quality cuisine on board is already an enhancing factor with regards to the in-flight experience, and according to the consensus, variety seems to amplify this even more.
- In addition, variety also seems to play a positive role in inclusivity in the sense that airlines would provide options that would pander to the passengers with restrictions on their diet, in respect to their religious beliefs or lifestyle choices.
- Variety also provides a wider window of experience with regards to culture as some airlines take the effort to implement a dichotomy of flavors and culture to the dishes they disseminate.
- Aside from variety and culture, presentation also plays an important role in perception, however considering the fact that the study is limited to economy class, expectations are set but they are not as critical in this study.

F. Cross Analysis

- It was found out that the informants are attracted to quality cuisine and most likely will fly with the same airline again due to their overall satisfaction with the airline's in-flight catering services. Additionally, one informant states that in-flight cuisine heavily compliments the entire service as well as any other forms of entertainment. However, on the contrary, one informant specifies that quality food helps initiate airline loyalty but mundane and repetitive food selection results in the fading of said loyalty.
- Based on the data findings, all informants reacted positively to the quality of food given on their respective flights. This in turn proves the connection between quality cuisine and customer satisfaction. However, when served with substandard food, informants have reacted negatively to the point where one informant won't ever fly with that same airline again.
- It was observed that a few of the informants have stated that the longer the flight, the more they want food on their trays. On the other hand, a shorter flight would not necessitate the need for food. This confirms the connection between the Review of Related Literature and the data collected. This also confirms that international flights are where quality cuisine must be served often to enhance passenger comfort throughout the flight.
- Although quality cuisine enhances the overall flight experience, the way the food is served to the customers is also very important. Along with the observations, one of the informants would often communicate with the cabin crew, and the more accommodating they were, the more satisfied the informant felt. This combats the repetitive nature of the airline's quality cuisine. By imparting provisions, the informant was assured that the additional cost for such a service would be worth it.
- According to the testimonies of the informants, airlines that provide delicious meals and a palatable experience are much more enticing to select and even re-book them again for future flights. This is in line with the notion that passengers are much more likely to book airlines that serve good quality food.

- While a variety of quality food is a welcome factor and enhancer of the overall flight experience, consideration should be given regarding the available options as they should be inclusive and cater to a wider audience. As such, the informants generally agree that the presence of choices that cater to specific diets whether it be of a religious, personal, or medical persuasion, enhances the positive effect that quality cuisine already brings to the flight experience.
- Taking this into account, the findings from the Review of Related Literature state that passengers are much more likely to be satisfied with their quality cuisine experience in flight if the airlines offer dishes that pander to their respective tastes and other intricate preferences.

CHAPTER FOUR DISCUSSION

A. Conclusions

Under the effect of quality cuisine on customer preference, the informants in the interviews agreed that quality cuisine significantly influences customer preference. Informants highlighted that good food enhances the overall flight experience, uplifts mood, and contributes to customer satisfaction. Quality cuisine can be a deciding factor in choosing to fly with the same airline again, especially on long-haul flights where comfort and experience are paramount.

For the impact of the provision of quality cuisine on customer airline selection, the provision of quality cuisine is seen as a positive attribute that can sway airline selection. Informants appreciate having meals included in the ticket, which adds convenience and enhances the overall travel experience. They value options that cater to diverse preferences and cultural backgrounds, indicating that airlines offering such quality and variety are likely to attract and retain customers.

In relevance of cultural appropriateness and presentation to customer perception of quality cuisine, cultural appropriateness, and presentation significantly influence customer perception of food quality. Informants emphasized the importance of having culturally relevant choices in food options, enhancing satisfaction by catering to diverse dietary preferences and cultural expectations provides a unique experience. The food presentation also matters as it reflects the airline's attention to detail and respect for cultural backgrounds, thereby contributing to overall satisfaction with the airline.

Thus, the results of the interviews highlight the necessity for airlines to prioritize not only comfortable seats and additional services but also the quality of in-flight meals. The results revealed that quality cuisine significantly enhances customer satisfaction, influences airline selection, and underscores the importance of cultural sensitivity in catering services, thereby enriching the overall flight experience.

B. Recommendations

Based on the insights gathered from the interviews regarding the impact of quality cuisine during in-flight catering on customer perception for full-service airlines from respective statements of the problem, the following recommendations are as follows:

- **Effect of Quality Cuisine on Customer Preference.** The recommendation to prioritize enhancing in-flight meal quality, including taste, presentation, and variety, aims to understand how these factors influence customer preference for airlines, particularly on long-haul flights. By improving meal quality, airlines can potentially increase passenger satisfaction and positively influence customer preferences and choices.
- **Impact on Customer Airline Selection.** Standardizing meal inclusion and ensuring cultural appropriateness in culinary options are proposed strategies to affect customer airline selection positively. These initiatives are expected to streamline the passenger experience, enhance convenience, and foster positive perceptions of the airline's service quality, potentially influencing repeat business and positive word-of-mouth recommendations.
- **Relevance of Cultural Appropriateness and Presentation.** Recognizing the significance of cultural appropriateness in food choices and presentation, the recommendation advocates for providing diverse culinary options that respect the cultural backgrounds of passengers. This approach is aimed at enriching the passenger experience, demonstrating inclusivity, and fostering positive perceptions and long-term customer loyalty toward the airline.

By addressing these recommendations, future research can provide insights into how airlines can strategically leverage in-flight catering to enhance customer experiences, perceptions of quality, and ultimately, airline selection. This comprehensive approach aims to inform airlines of effective strategies that elevate their competitive edge and cultivate deeper relationships with passengers rooted in satisfaction and cultural sensitivity.

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**APPENDIX
APPENDIX A: RRL MATRIX**

Review of Related Literature	Statement of the Problem	Questionnaire
<p>Based on (Gamal, H. E., 2021), service quality is key to attract and keep loyal customers (Chang and Yeh, 2002; Gursoy et al., 2005; Liou and Tzang, 2007). On-board food is an important dimension of airline services. In particular, Solomon (2002) noted that passengers generally will choose the airline that offers the best food. Further, on-board food services now are seen as part of marketing strategies in attracting all kinds of travelers (Jones, 1995). In this regard, King (2001) reported that some passengers would be willing to change airlines, alter travel patterns and even pay more money for the high quality of on-board food served.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is the effect of quality cuisine on customer preference? ● How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In your opinion with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not? ● Considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline?
<p>In-flight meal satisfaction was found to significantly contribute to the prediction of passengers’ flight satisfaction and loyalty, especially meal taste, preferences, and service. The strength and significance of this prediction varied according to flight details and passengers’ travel habits and individual characteristics; such as the airline company, seat class, route, trip purpose, flight duration, flying experience in general and with the airline, travel party, and passengers’ socio-demographics. (Al Balushi, H. J. G. 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is the effect of quality cuisine on customer preference? ● How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In your opinion with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not? ● Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase? If so, what are these provisions?
<p>There are significant differences between flight distances and preferred foods, nutrition dimension, hygiene/sanitation dimension, menu, supplementary service dimension, employee dimension. Importance of dimensions rises together with the longer flight distances. (Sariođlan, M., 2018)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is the effect of quality cuisine on customer preference? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● During long-haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience?
<p>In other words, in-flight food and beverage quality is becoming essential for airlines in the effort to attract customers and outperform airline competitors. In the highly competitive airline industry, satisfying existing and potential passengers should be the priority of a full-service airline business that aims to stimulate repeat purchase. (Han et al., 2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase? If so, what are these provisions?
<p>The empirical results and findings suggest that there is a significant impact of service quality on passenger satisfaction and loyalty in the Indian aviation industry. The result further shows that empathy and responsiveness are the prominent factors of service quality which is a vital prerequisite for customer satisfaction. (Walia et al., 2021)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline? ● During long-haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
<p>Based on (Hwang, E.; Kim, Y.-S.; Song, H.G. 2023), well-designed inflight food service highly correlates with overall service quality and satisfaction for business and economy-class travelers (Park, J.W. 2007). These airline passengers presented the highest perceived value for onboard meal service (Chen, C.F.; Wu, T.F. 2009).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?

<p>Designing an in-flight menu is akin to crafting a work of art. The menu not only needs to cater to a diverse range of tastes and dietary preferences but also consider the challenges of serving food at high altitudes. Airlines collaborate with expert chefs and nutritionists to curate menus that are not only delicious but also nutritionally balanced. From tantalizing appetizers to delectable desserts, every dish is meticulously chosen to ensure passenger satisfaction. (Team, L. (2023b, December 20). Airplane Food: Behind the scenes of In-Flight catering. How to Make a Paper Airplane.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How is cultural appropriateness and presentation relevant to the customer’s perception of quality? ● How will the provision of quality cuisine affect customer airline selection? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How does the cultural appropriateness of inflight food and its quality influence customers' perceptions of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline? ● How satisfied are you with the variety of food options available on flights you’ve taken?
<p>Economy Class passengers are also treated to satisfying meals that cater to diverse tastes. These guests can select from international dishes like Chinese, Indian Subcontinent, or vegetarian meals, depending on their preferences. Emirates ensures dietary requirements for passengers with special needs like gluten-friendly, low lactose, or medically necessary dietary restrictions, are met. [Carl. (2023, November 23). Do Emirates provide food: In-Flight dining options explained. TravelSpock.]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How is cultural appropriateness and presentation relevant to the customer’s perception of quality? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How does the cultural appropriateness of inflight food and its quality influence customers' perceptions of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?
<p>Another type of cultural is medical diets, including low/high fiber, low fat/cholesterol, diabetic, peanut free, non-lactose, low salt/sodium, low-purine, low-calorie, low-protein and gluten-free meals. Religious diets, including kosher food, Hindu, Buddhist and halal food and Asian vegetarian meals. Some airlines do not offer a specific meal for non-vegan vegetarians; instead, they are given a vegan meal. (Gunardi, Ariawan, & Martono, K. (2018, June 26). Airlines Meals Service: LEGAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS. UGC Approved Journal.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How is cultural appropriateness and presentation relevant to the customer’s perception of quality? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How does the cultural appropriateness of inflight food and its quality influence customers' perceptions of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?

APPENDIX B: PILOT TEST RESULTS

- **Legend:** 1 - Remove Statement | 2 - Change Statement | 3 - Useful with Revisions | 4 - Very Useful
- **P1:** Ms. Menchie O. Solidum | Instructor, Senior High School Department
- **P2:** Ms. Jermaine Anne T. Tarriela | Instructor, Senior High School Department
- **P3:** Ms. Jackie Krystle F. Lumosbog | Instructor, BS Air Transportation Department

List of Questions	P1	P2	P3	Results
Q1. How significant is the quality of in-flight cuisine to your overall experience with an airline?	4	4	4	4
Q2. How likely would you suggest an airline based only on its high-end dining service?	4	3	1	3
Q3. How much do you believe high-end meal service improves your overall travel experience?	4	3	4	4
Q4. How does the quality of inflight food and beverage services impact passengers' experience and satisfaction in the airline industry?	4	4	3	4
Q5. How would you evaluate your recent high-end food service experience on a flight?	4	4	3	4
Q6. In what ways does quality food in inflight influence the preferable choice in selecting an airline, especially long-haul flights?	4	3	1	3
Q7. How important is high-end food service in comparison to other in-flight amenities like seating comfort and entertainment?	4	4	1	3
Q8. How would you rate the professionalism of the staff serving high-end food on flights you've taken?	4	4	3	4
Q9. How does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?	4	4	4	4
Q10. To what extent does high-end food service influence your choice of airline?	4	3	1	3
Q11. How satisfied are you with the variety of meal options available on your recent flights, and how does this influence your choice of the airline?	4	3	3	3
Q12. To what extent do you believe that cultural aspects impact the variety and quality of in-flight meals, and does this influence your choice of airline?	4	4	3	4
Q13. How would you rate the presentation of high-end food service on flights you've experienced?	4	4	1	3
Q14. How important is it for you that the food service and menu (variety of food) changes seasonally or regularly?	4	4	4	4
Q15. In what ways does the provision of quality cuisine, including accommodating diverse dietary preferences and medical or religious dietary needs, affect passengers' airline selection and loyalty?	4	4	2	3
Q16. How satisfied are you with the portion sizes of high-end food served on flights you've experienced?	4	3	1	3
Q17. How does the cultural appropriateness of inflight food and its quality influence customers' perceptions of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?	4	3	4	4
Q18. How important is the inclusion of local or culturally relevant cuisine in high-end in-flight food service?	4	4	1	3
Q19. To what length are customers willing to go change their preferred airlines or pay more for good and quality food inflight?	4	4	4	4
Q20. Has the customer service of the in-flight meals made you choose the airlines again in the future?	4	4	1	3
Q21. How significant is the efficiency of high-end food service delivery to your in-flight experience?	4	4	4	4
Q22. How important is the pairing of food with their corresponding beverages (e.g., juices, sodas) to your in-flight dining experience?	4	4	4	4
Q23. How likely are you to pay extra for a flight with high-end food service?	4	4	1	3

Q24. Does high-end cuisine affect your perception of economy classes within legacy airlines?	4	4	4	4
Q25. How likely are you to choose an airline offering high-end food service over one that does not?	4	3	2	3
Q26. Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase?	4	4	4	4
Q27. Does a competitive edge in the quality of an airline's food be a deciding factor for the selection of an airline?	4	4	4	4
Q28. During long-haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience?	4	4	4	4
Q29. How important is it to you that an airline offers specific meals catering to your medical or religious dietary needs when choosing which airline to fly with?	4	3	4	4
Q30. How satisfied are you with the variety of food options available on flights you've taken?	4	4	4	4
Q31. How does your satisfaction with the nutritional balance and taste of in-flight meals influence your overall perception of the airline?	4	4	4	4

APPENDIX C: INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

FINAL INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR WORKING PROFESSIONALS AND STUDENTS

- During long-haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
- Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase? If so, what are these provisions?
- How can you say that you are satisfied by the variety of options available on flights you've taken?
- In your opinion with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not?
- How does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?
- Considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline?
- How does the cultural appropriateness of inflight food and its quality influence customers' perceptions of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?

APPENDIX D: INFORMED CONSENT FORM

ATRN 417 - IA | Group 4

Amodia | De Dios | Nilo | Nuñez | Pocong | Poliran | Ticsay

Participant Consent Form

FLIGHT, FOOD & FLAVOR: THE IMPACT OF QUALITY CUISINE DURING IN-FLIGHT CATERING ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION FOR FULL-SERVICE AIRLINES

The information contained, collected, used, shared, disclosed, and stored in this form are held confidential and intended only for the purpose of this study, in compliance to the standard prescribed by the Data Privacy Act 2012.

Do you give your consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of your personal information?

- Yes, I fully give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.
No, I do not give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.

Please read the following statements:

- I, Emmanuel Thaddeus O. Bernal voluntarily agreed to be one of the participant/s in this research study.
I understand that:
Even if I agree to participate, I can withdraw or refuse anytime to answer any questions without any kind of consequences.
The participation will involve the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-flight Catering to Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines as stated.
I will not benefit directly from participating in this research study.
All information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
Signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in the study of this research paper.
A transcript of my interview in which all identifying information will be shown as it is.
Under the Freedom of Information Legislation (Freedom of Information Act 2009), I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time as specified above.
I have the right to contact any people involved in this research study to seek further clarification and information.
This form will serve as the official record of consent of this interview.

I have read the information above and agree on becoming a participant of this study.

Signature of the Participant

ATRN 417 - 1A | Group 4

Amodia | De Dios | Nilo | Nafiez | Pocong | Polivan | Ticay

Participant Consent Form

FLIGHT, FOOD & FLAVOR: THE IMPACT OF QUALITY CUISINE DURING IN-FLIGHT CATERING ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION FOR FULL-SERVICE AIRLINES

The information contained, collected, used, shared, disclosed, and stored in this form are held confidential and intended only for the purpose of this study, in compliance to the standard prescribed by the Data Privacy Act 2012.

Do you give your consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of your personal information?

- Yes, I fully give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.
- No, I do not give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.

Please read the following statements:

- I, Jerric A. Pineda, voluntarily agreed to be one of the participant/s in this research study.
- I understand that:
 - Even if I agree to participate, I can withdraw or refuse anytime to answer any questions without any kind of consequences.
 - The participation will involve the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-flight Catering to Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines as stated.
 - I will not benefit directly from participating in this research study.
 - All information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
 - Signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in the study of this research paper.
 - A transcript of my interview in which all identifying information will be shown as it is.
 - Under the Freedom of Information Legislation (Freedom of Information Act 2009), I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time as specified above.
 - I have the right to contact any people involved in this research study to seek further clarification and information.
 - This form will serve as the official record of consent of this interview.

I have read the information above and agree on becoming a participant of this study.

Signature of the Participant

ATRN 417 - 1A | Group 4

Amodia | De Dios | Nilo | Noller | Pocong | Pafiran | Ticsay

Participant Consent Form

**FLIGHT, FOOD & FLAVOR: THE IMPACT OF QUALITY CUISINE DURING
IN-FLIGHT CATERING ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION FOR FULL-SERVICE
AIRLINES**

The information contained, collected, used, shared, disclosed, and stored in this form are held confidential and intended only for the purpose of this study, in compliance to the standard prescribed by the Data Privacy Act 2012.

Do you give your consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of your personal information?

- Yes, I fully give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.
- No, I do not give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.

Please read the following statements:

- I, *Belenje L. Hernandez* voluntarily agreed to be one of the participant/s in this research study.
- I understand that:
 - Even if I agree to participate, I can withdraw or refuse anytime to answer any questions without any kind of consequences.
 - The participation will involve the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-flight Catering to Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines as stated.
 - I will not benefit directly from participating in this research study.
 - All information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
 - Signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in the study of this research paper.
 - A transcript of my interview in which all identifying information will be shown as it is.
 - Under the Freedom of Information Legislation (Freedom of Information Act 2009), I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time as specified above.
 - I have the right to contact any people involved in this research study to seek further clarification and information.
 - This form will serve as the official record of consent of this interview.

I have read the information above and agree on becoming a participant of this study.

Signature of the Participant

ATRN 417 - IA | Group 4

Amadio | De Dios | Nilo | Nolez | Pocang | Poliran | Ticsay

Participant Consent Form

FLIGHT, FOOD & FLAVOR: THE IMPACT OF QUALITY CUISINE DURING IN-FLIGHT CATERING ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION FOR FULL-SERVICE AIRLINES

The information contained, collected, used, shared, disclosed, and stored in this form are held confidential and intended only for the purpose of this study, in compliance to the standard prescribed by the Data Privacy Act 2012.

Do you give your consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of your personal information?

- Yes, I fully give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.
- No, I do not give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.

Please read the following statements:

- I, NIGEL NIQUICO voluntarily agreed to be one of the participant/s in this research study.
- I understand that:
 - Even if I agree to participate, I can withdraw or refuse anytime to answer any questions without any kind of consequences.
 - The participation will involve the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-flight Catering to Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines as stated.
 - I will not benefit directly from participating in this research study.
 - All information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
 - Signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in the study of this research paper.
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 Signature of the Participant

ATRN 417 - IA | Group 4

Amodia | De Dios | Nilo | Nufier | Pocong | Poliran | Tlesay

Participant Consent Form

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- Yes, I fully give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.
- No, I do not give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.

Please read the following statements:

- I, Jonathan Milla Pison voluntarily agreed to be one of the participant/s in this research study.
- I understand that:
 - Even if I agree to participate, I can withdraw or refuse anytime to answer any questions without any kind of consequences.
 - The participation will involve the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-flight Catering to Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines as stated.
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I have read the information above and agree on becoming a participant of this study.

Signature of the Participant

ATRN 417 - 1A | Group 4

Amodia | De Dios | Nilo | Nofez | Pocong | Poliran | Ticsay

Participant Consent Form

FLIGHT, FOOD & FLAVOR: THE IMPACT OF QUALITY CUISINE DURING IN-FLIGHT CATERING ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION FOR FULL-SERVICE AIRLINES

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- Yes, I fully give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.
- No, I do not give my consent for the processing, releasing, and/or retention of my personal information.

Please read the following statements:

- I, KHASMIR D. GELLA voluntarily agreed to be one of the participant/s in this research study.
- I understand that:
 - Even if I agree to participate, I can withdraw or refuse anytime to answer any questions without any kind of consequences.
 - The participation will involve the Impact of Quality Cuisine during In-flight Catering to Customer Perception for Full-Service Airlines as stated.
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Signature of the Participant

APPENDIX D: INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPT**Informant 1 (Student)****Passenger aboard a Flight (In-flight Food Cuisine)****Researcher/s: Christian James N. Nilo & Emanuel M. Ticsay**

- **Interviewer:** So good morning, thank you for joining our interview today. First, can you introduce yourself, state your name followed by your age and occupation?
- **Interviewee:** So I am Emmanuel Santiago Brual and I am twenty years old and an incoming fourth (4th) year student of Aeronautical Engineering in PATTS.
- **Interviewer:** Okay so for our introductory question, um... did you uhh... have you ever experienced cuisine or any food from international flight via legacy carrier, specifically in economy class?
- **Interviewee:** Yes. I am always out of the country.
- **Interviewer:** Ahh, so that's good to know, may I ask which specific airline that is?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... there is a lot since I have taken a few several long-haul flights within the past few weeks. So I took um... one of them is Eva Air. So we flew from Manila to Taipei then Taipei to San Francisco uhh... a few weeks ago– I mean last month *pala* (rather).
- **Interviewer:** Ahh... thank you for that uhh... now that we're about to ask a few more questions starting with the first question. During the long-haul flights that you have taken, do you think that the quality of the cuisine significantly uhh... is significant to a better flight experience? So why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... yes it really plays a huge part in the experience because uhm... considering that it's a legacy carrier, of course, many passengers will expect quality service, and a lot of them like me uhh... we don't really pack food for our flights uhm... we need to know that uhm... ticket is worth it so we expect them to serve food and the quality of the food uhm... it affects your experience especially in a long-haul flight.
- **Interviewer:** Ok thank you, thank you for that. So the second question uhm... ahh... is the provision of in-flight food service be included as part of the ticket an appealing offer, factor to purchase the ticket? If so, uhh... what are those provisions?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... so uhm... its an appealing uhh... factor for purchase wait uhm... what do you mean by provisions?
- **Interviewer:** Provisions uhh... provisions that they uhh... have given meaning they have provided the food to you.
- **Interviewee:** Yeah for me uhm... it's an uhm... very uhm... very uhh... appealing factor usually they list it, it's already included in the process of booking uhm... its explicitly state in the ticket that in-flight meals will be provided and uhh... in most cases you have options to alter the uhh... food choices if you have dietary restrictions but for me i don't have that.
- **Interviewer:** Uhh... thank you for that. Now how can you say that you are satisfied with the, as you said, the variety of food that can be given to you and how important it is for you for the airline experience as a whole?
- **Interviewee:** Umm... so hmm... im hmm... wait let me process my thoughts. Uhm... I'm not really a picky eater as long as there is a uhm... as long as there is food specifically like full course meals when it comes to a long-haul flight and then I'm kind of easy to please as long as the basic stuff uhm... are included and that's all. That's pretty much it.
- **Interviewer:** So when it comes to, uhh... additional question, uhm... above the uhh... any type of food and specifically any type of food is alright for you just as long as they provide the food for you?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.

- **Interviewer:** Oh, ok uhh... next question. Uhm... how does your experience with in-flight food quality, as it said, as the food quality itself influence your intention to fly again with the airline? So how does it affect your decision to take that airline again in the future?
- **Interviewee:** So uhh... if the food is great I'd be enticed to fly on the same airline because uhh... especially when you're flying long-haul because if the food is nice it can help you get through a very long flight and it makes uhm... sitting down for like more than 10 hours bearable.
- **Interviewer:** Uhh... I'd like to ask another additional question to that, so can you give us a specific ahh... occurrence that this has happened to you that you chose that airline specifically because of you enjoyed the experience, particularly the food they gave to you?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... to be honest we don't really take the same uhm... airline again but if we do it's not because of the food it's because of the uhm... uhh... of how uhh... because of the ticket price and the availability.
- **Interviewer:** So with that considering, uhh... considering that, does the quality of that in-flight cuisine typically translate to, in your opinion, uhh... more expensive tickets, do you think that has influence in your choice in selecting the airlines because it has a higher, higher price of the ticket because of the meal that is included in the ticket itself?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... when deciding for tickets uhm... it's not usually me who decides so uhh... it's usually my parents and uhm... honestly if it's a legacy carrier we assume that the food is already included because uhm... especially when it's a long-haul flight so we just look into the ticket prices cause there was a recent incident I had with an airline a few weeks ago, it's a legacy carrier but they never served anything in the entire flight when we flew from Mexico to uhh... Argentina, via Avianca Airlines did not serve it wasn't stated and it's pretty disappointing for uhh... legacy airline.
- **Interviewer:** So in that sense uhh... the lack of provision of the in-flight meal, particularly that airline, a full service airline to add, did it degrade your experience as a whole flying with that airline?
- **Interviewee:** I do not like Avianca Air because not only they did not serve food but they also overcharged us for carry-on baggage which was something we never experienced on other flights.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you for the info. So when it comes to this last question, uhh... how does the cultural appropriateness of the in-flight food itself and its quality influence your perception to the food quality given to you and your satisfaction with the airline?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... the cultural appropriateness because I know that airlines tend to serve food from the destination or to the destination of the place you're going so I'm having some experiences with Middle Eastern Airlines such as Saudia and Etihad wherein they serve uhh... Filipino food when we were connecting from the Philippines to Europe and uhm... seeing Filipino food being served in a foreign airline it made me appreciate the airline more and it affected my overall perception of how they care for their passengers and how uhm... excellent they are as an airline.
- **Interviewer:** So in a sense that elevates your perception and expectation for the airline that gives cultural appropriateness and food quality to your experience as a customer?
- **Interviewee:** Yes because uhm... it makes it shows that they are culturally aware of the passengers they are serving and their backgrounds and the thing that they wanted the passengers to feel at home despite being in a foreign country.
- **Interviewer:** So uhh... okay thank you. That would be the last question uhh... an additional question of mine uhh... particularly when it comes to your experience as a passenger. As in general, does the food itself in the airline make you stay or even elevate their perception as a carrier and not particularly as a way of transport from A to B?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... to be honest, when it's uhh... a shorter flight, I don't really mind about food because uhm... because uhm... it's just a short flight but when it's a longer flight, uhh... type of food they serve can affect my perception of them because uhm... it shows how much they care for passenger experience especially as someone who has flown in economy class it shows how much they care and they want to elevate the experience for their passengers.
- **Interviewer:** Ok so that would be all uhh... thank you Mr. Brual for uhh... participating in this interview ahh... thank you for insights uhh... thank you and good morning.

Informant 2 (Student)
Passenger aboard a Flight (In-flight Food Cuisine)
Researcher/s: John Roy P. De Dios, Andrei Bea D. Nuñez & Christian James N. Nilo

- **Interviewer:** Good morning. Thank you for joining us today but first can you please introduce yourself? State your name followed by age and occupation.
- **Interviewee:** I'm Gelmyr Ignacio Fernandez uhm.. I'm twenty-one years old and still a student.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you. For our introductory question, did you ever experience eating cuisine or food for an international flight via legacy airliner economy class?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** If so may I ask what airline it is?
- **Interviewee:** PAL and Cathay Pacific.
- **Interviewer:** With that said we are about to ask you a few questions regarding your experience, so let's have question number one. During long haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, I think it is *mas* (more) enjoyable *yung* (the) experience especially when *kapag mainit na yung ulo mo* (when your head is heated) and if delayed *yung* flight, *babawi sila* (they will make up for it) *sa* (in) food.
- **Interviewer:** Ohh... interesting. Let's move on to the second question, is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase? If so, what are these provisions?
- **Interviewee:** Yes it is an appealing factor that can influence the decision to purchase *kasi hindi mo na kailangan maglabas ng* (because you don't have to show) money in-flight not like *sa mga* (to those) low cost airlines.
- **Interviewer:** I see I see. Third question. How can you say that you are satisfied by the variety of options available on flights you've taken?
- **Interviewee:** If I would rate it from one to ten, I'd give it an eight, though it varies between airlines. *Yung iba kasi dalawa lang yung* (the others have only two) options *mo* then *yung sa iba sobrang daming* (the others have so many) options.
- **Interviewer:** Hmm... I see, I see. Moving on to the fourth, In your opinion, with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** It is very important. As a *foodie syempre* (food-lover, of course) I'll take a picture *ganun* (like that) of course *dapat mabubusog ka* (you must be full) and happy *ka sa post mo* (you are happy with your post).
- **Interviewer:** Ahh... Okay. Moving on to the fifth question. How does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?
- **Interviewee:** Umm... positive and memorable experiences *din talaga* (too really). *Yung* (The) taste of course and how the cabin crew asked you or and serve the food to you.
- **Interviewer:** Ahh... so presentation plays a part okay. Uhh... sixth. Considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline?
- **Interviewee:** Especially if they value culinary experiences and if *foodie ka talaga* (you really love food). *Katulad nga ng sinabi ko kanina* (Just like what I have said earlier) I love taking pictures before *ako kumain* (I eat). *Tapos pino-post ko pa ganun* (Then I will post it like that).

- **Interviewer:** Ahh... so last question. How does the cultural appropriateness of in-flight food and its quality influence customer's perception of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?
- **Interviewee:** When airlines cater to diverse food cultural tastes and dietary needs it enhances the travel experience, making passengers feel valued and respected. Which can lead higher uhh... customer loyalty and positive reviews. Based on my experience with PAL, *pagbalik ko* from Korea to Manila, the food that they served is Korean food. So feel *mo pa rin talaga na nagtravel ka and mga kasabayan mo din kasi* (you still really feel that you are traveling with other co-travellers too) is Korean tapos *sa* (in) Cathay Pacific *naman* (likewise), *sobrang daming* (there are many) choices uhm... *meron dun* (are there) if vegetarian *ka ganun* (if you are vegetarian like that).
- **Interviewer:** Nice. Okay that seems to be about it, thank you for your participation in this research.
- **Interviewer:** Uhh... yes thank you. Uhm... may I ask actually *sa* (in) number three question. When you say that you are satisfied like you said eight out of ten right? How can you say so that it's eight out of ten? When it comes to satisfaction.
- **Interviewee:** *Medyo konti yung* (Quite a bit of) serving.
- **Interviewer:** Ohh I see.
- **Interviewer:** So serving *na* (that) portions?
- **Interviewee:** *Pero kasi* (But because) economy class *nga* (in such a manner) so expectations.
- **Interviewer:** So it's eight out of ten *kasi dahil nga sa* (because of the) servings?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** *Pero* (But) that means the rest is up to par?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** Ok, I see.
- **Interviewer:** Between those two airlines that you mentioned, PAL and Cathay, assuming its the same route as Korea to Manila and Manila to Korea-
- **Interviewee:** Ahh... *yung isa* (the other one) is uhh... is Manila to Hong Kong. Cathay Pacific.
- **Interviewer:** But in terms of preference, which would you rate higher? Cathay's uhh... wider array or uhm... PAL's uhh... detailed service?
- **Interviewee:** As a Filipino *syempre* (of course) PAL *pero pag sa* (but if its) service, Cathay Pacific.
- **Interviewer:** Okay thank you. I think that is all, is there more? No? Okay, that is all. Thank you again mister...?
- **Interviewee:** Fernandez.
- **Interviewer:** Mr. Fernandez, thank you for your participation. Your answers are valued thank you. Thank you, have a good day.

Informant 3 (Student)
Passenger aboard a Flight (In-flight Food Cuisine)
Researcher/s: John Roy P. De Dios & Christian James N. Nilo

- **Interviewer:** Good evening thank you for joining us today, but first can you please introduce yourself, state your name followed by your age and occupation.
- **Interviewee:** So Im Josette A. Fernandez, I am twenty two years old and I'm a student.
- **Interviewer:** Okay I see. For our introductory question, did you ever experience eating cuisine or food for an international flight via legacy airliner, economy class?
- **Interviewee:** What do you mean by cuisine food? Is it like specific cuisine or any type of cuisine?
- **Interviewer:** Any type of cuisine.
- **Interviewee:** Oh, I experience po from Emirates, so its more on middle eastern type of cuisine, and *ano naman siya* (it's like what) uhm... its not fully arabic...there's *ano* (what) there's uhm... choices, you can either get halal food for like muslims and you can get more on pork or beef or just like that. Yeah, I have experienced it.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you, how many long-haul flights per year have you experienced during the post pandemic period? Is it two flights per year, three flights or more than that?
- **Interviewee:** It depends on *ano siguro kasi* (what maybe because) like my mom is usually going here *pero minsan* (but sometimes) we go there so it depends on maybe *kapag pumupunta kami doon* (when we go there) so like two flights per year.
- **Interviewer:** Two flights per year okay thank you. If so, may I ask what airline it is?
- **Interviewee:** *Hindi siya isang airline lang* (It's not only one airline), so like maybe *minsan* (sometimes) Etihad *cuz* (because) like it's from there. Eh, from *kung dun ka sa* (if you are in) UAE it's more on cheaper *kapag yung kanilang* (if that) airline *yung kukunin mo* (you want to choose). Like here in Philippines, if you book in Cebu Pac *ganun* it's much cheaper, so if there *siguro* (maybe) Emirates and Etihad.
- **Interviewer:** Got it, okay. With that said, we're about to ask you a few questions regarding your experience. Uhh... question number one. During long haul flights or international flights do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** I feel like uhm... its part of the experience, *siguro* (maybe) for me its... it makes my experience way better *kasi* (because) it *siguro naman pag pagod ka* (maybe of you are tired) from all that *byahe* (travel) you would want a hot meal a good quality meal. For me I think it bumps up my experience, it makes me want to experience it again.
- **Interviewer:** I see, so it's important to you?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah, I think it is important, it's actually *parang* (like) more on *nag o-open* (it opens) up *yung* (the) plate *mo* (for you) for another type of cuisine like it's a new thing I think so.
- **Interviewer:** I see, okay. Next question. Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor purchase? If so, what are these provisions?
- **Interviewee:** What do you mean by provisions?
- **Interviewer:** So lets say presentation of the food itself to you, or how the flight attendants provide the food to you.
- **Interviewee:** Oh, like in terms of plating?

- **Interviewer:** Yeah, do you think of that being part of the ticket, its an appealing factor to you?
- **Interviewer:** I feel like as uhh... *siguro* (maybe) like economy *lang siguro* (like that), I don't feel like *yung* (the) the way they plate it is appealing *kasi* (because) like its economy. Unlike business or first class, I don't think it's appealing, *ang nakaka-drawn siguro ng ano* (maybe it attracts) more people to get economy in that specific airline and like the quality food *lang siguro* (maybe just quality food) Like the hot meal, the choices, and like sometimes they give their own spin *sa ano* (on what) they give their own arabic bread like that which is nice.
- **Interviewer:** I see so for you *mas importante yung pagkain mismo* (the food for you is more important) instead of the presentation that they provide?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah I think so *cuz* (because) who would want a cone?
- **Interviewer:** True, okay so question number three. How can you say that you are satisfied with the variety of the options available on flights you've taken?
- **Interviewee:** I think I'm satisfied to know that there's a lot of variety, especially for those vegetarian or like those with diets na they can't really consume like those uhh veg- sometimes there's people like they can't eat such hard foods, I think it's more appealing to me *na may mga nagagawa silang bagay* (that they would do something) to help those people that is lacking *yung mga kailangan talaga nila* (with their needs) or they want soft food, they can accommodate it or like in babies they can heat up their milk. I feel like that's accommodating and I think one aspect *din yung tinitingnan ng Emirates* (that Emirates consider) for me is *yung* (the) for Muslims, especially for Muslims *kasi* (because) they need to eat halal food which is you know they can't.
- **Interviewer:** Non-Pork?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah, non-pork. There's- *ni minsan hindi naman siya* (sometimes it's not) actually pork *pero* (but) some food *na bawal talaga sa kanila* (it's not allowed for them) so they have to be very specific with the choices that they give their Muslim customers.
- **Interviewer:** I see so the variety of options, what do you think is more important, the taste of the food or the variety of options they have?
- **Interviewee:** I think both.
- **Interviewer:** Both, both are equally important?
- **Interviewee:** Both are equally important *cuz* (because) like *anong gagawin natin sa* (this much food if it's not quality). But I- who wants *ano masakit yung tiyan pag nag t-travel* (having stomach ache during the travel), I don't think anyone wants that.
- **Interviewer:** That's true okay thank you. Question number five. Actually, question number four. In your opinion, with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** I'm sorry again again?
- **Interviewer:** In your opinion, with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** So, we're talking about quality of food?
- **Interviewer:** Yes, quality, how important is it to you in your flight experience?
- **Interviewee:** I might think it is important as much as like safety, *kasi* (because) quality in food makes us feel better if we're eating good quality food like or when we feel better *kasi* (because) we're up there *diba* (right) so our- *ang* taste buds *natin* (our taste buds) like I think lower?
- **Interviewer:** Yeah, it's different.

- **Interviewee:** It's different so I feel like the better quality the food is you will enjoy it up there even *kasi* stuffy *siya kapag* (because it's stuffy when) long haul flight *diba* (right). It's very stuffy *sa loob ng* (inside the) plane so we have to be like, oh I'm just gonna eat to make my mood better *ganun* (like that) I feel like that is it other than being sad there for like eight hours *siguro* (maybe eight hours). I feel like food makes us you know *madami siyang-* (there like many) instead of like bad hormones *yung na r-release* (releasing bad hormones), if we eat food we would be happy and like not angry all the time.
- **Interviewer:** I see so your airline experience or *yung* comfort *mo* (your comfort) the food enhances it so much?
Interviewee: Yeah I think it dies.
- **Interviewer:** Ok thank you next question, question number five. How does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?
- **Interviewee:** *Siguro ano*, (I feel like) a good quality food *parang* (like) it gives it gains trust *sa mga* customer (to the customers) like, oh *ang sarap ng* food *dito* (the food here is delicious), *ang ganda ng* customer service (it has good customer service), I feel like that draws people like *paano ba sila mag-serve* (how they will serve), *paano sila mag accommodate ng* (how they will accommodate) customers I feel like *ano* (what) that is also part of being having a good quality food.
- **Interviewer:** I see so does it contribute to your loyalty?
- **Interviewee:** I think so yeah.
- **Interviewer:** So, you would stick with an airline if they have really good food or service whilst in flight?
- **Interviewee:** I think there's many factors as like you know financial, I think if I have enough money to have like to go in a legacy airline everytime *siguro* (maybe) I will do I will choose that same airline.
- **Interviewer:** Alright thank you, question number six. Considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline?
- **Interviewee:** *Siguro ano* (I think maybe) it depends on the priority at that moment, it depends on the priority on what you should spend more what you should spend less, I feel like if you have enough you know financial support or enough *yung mga ano pera mo* (the money that you have) at that time I think you can go and splurge on yourself more.
- **Interviewer:** I see uhh... additional question to that. So, let's say we're comparing the food right, let's say the quality of the food is the same the airline is the same. Would you enjoy that food better if it's a long flight or if it's a short flight?
- **Interviewee:** I feel like long.
- **Interviewer:** Long, so you would enjoy the food more if it was a long flight?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah, I feel like I can- *kasi pag* long haul flight (if it's long-haul flight) there's a lot of variety food, it's not the same, I think it is not the same, *kunwari* (for example) lunch dinner won't be the same. I want *kapag* (when) short haul it's only one meal *ganun* (like that), so I think I don't think I'll enjoy it as much as long haul, I won't have the variety, I won't taste like the different, *ay ganto pala kinakain nila sa* dinner (oh this kind of food that they eat for dinner) *ay ganto pala kinakain nila sa* lunch (oh this kind of food that they will eat for lunch). I feel like *siguro yun* (maybe that).
- **Interviewer:** I see so when it comes to expensive tickets *mas* (more) worth it *kapag pagkain na masarap nasa* (if the food is delicious for) long haul flight?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah I think so.
- **Interviewer:** Ok so for question number seven. Last question. How does cultural appropriateness of in-flight food and its quality influence customers' perception of food and overall satisfaction with the airline?

- **Interviewee:** Perception in food... *siguro ano* (maybe what) as a person na goes *kunwari* (for example) your filipino you're going with Emirates airlines *siguro* (maybe) you would *ano- ma c-culture shock siguro ay ganto pala lasa niyan* (you will be culture shock like oh, this what it taste like), I feel like *nag i-iba pa as nag i-iba siya kasi* (its still differ and still differs because) we are not used to the taste I think we're not used to the taste ng food *nila* (from them) so I feel like its a fifty-fifty *na* (that) they will like it they will not so I feel like its ahh... my line between people's taste *kung ano ba yung mga gusto nila, pero siguro* (what they like, but I think) for me I'm open *sa* (on) trying new things, especially *sa* (on) food, *kung paano nila gawin yung food nila sa* (on how they will make their food on) long haul I feel like I am open with that. *Ang* (The) perception *naman ng tao* (of people) it surely depends *naman siguro doon sa tao* (I think for the people).
- **Interviewer:** I see, for you though?
- **Interviewee:** For me I feel like *ano kasi* (what because) I'm an open person *sa* (on) like I will be happy to try it *pero* (but) if I'm if I don't like it and then *huwag pilitin* (don't force it).
- **Interviewer:** Yeah that's true.
- **Interviewee:** *Huwag pilitin, huwag natin pilitin* (Do not force it, let us not force them).
- **Interviewer:** *Pero* (But) you are appreciative *na pinapakita nila yung* (that they are showing the) culture *sa pagkain* (on food) towards you?
- **Interviewee:** I think so, that makes an airline unique I feel like that *ano* (what) it doesn't *kunwari pag sinasabi natin* (for example, when we say) Singapore, I think they should *ano* (what) try to open their own twist *sa mga gantong bagay* (for these things) which makes them more *yung mga ano ng tao parang, ay ang ganda pala ng food dito, ay ang sarap pala, parang dun sila ma i-intrigue* (what like the people will say, oh the food is good here, oh the food is delicious, like that will make them intrigue).
- **Interviewer:** I see I see, so additional question to that, let's say it's a new type of food that you haven't eaten before, you tried it but you didn't really like it, its high quality *pero* you didn't really like it. Are you still satisfied with the airline? The fact that they tried to give you that cultural appropriateness in food towards you?
- **Interviewee:** I don't really like it?... *Siguro ano* (I think maybe) feedback is the best thing you can do, *pero* (but) in terms of *siguro maganda naman* (maybe of good) service *pero* (but) got that term *na hindi mo siya gusto* (it's not what you like) is a personal preferences, it doesn't *ano* (what) suit everyone *siguro* (maybe) that won't affect as much *kasi-* (because) *oo* (yes) that won't affect as much *kasi* (because) high quality *naman siya* (it's high quality) best ingredients or whatever I feel like it's personal preference, *siguro* (maybe) feedback *na lang* (just give feedback) next time, *ay* (oh) I don't like this as much.
- **Interviewer:** Yeah, so better options?
- **Interviewee:** Better options, maybe you can *ano* (what) ask *na lang* (them) different food.
- **Interviewer:** Different food yeah, I see I see, so I think that's it do you have additional questions? [De Dios says no]... So that's about it thank you once again Ms. Fernandez for this interview and have a good evening.
- **Interviewee:** Thank you.

Informant 4 (Working Professional)
Passenger aboard a Flight (In-flight Food Cuisine)
Researcher/s: Rose Anne A. Pocong & Emanuel M. Ticsay

- **Interviewer:** So good afternoon! Thank you for joining us today but first, can you please introduce yourself? So, state your name, your age, and occupation.
- **Interviewee:** My name is Khasmir Gella, I am specifically an Engineer. I'm twenty-seven years old and I currently work here in PATTS College of Aeronautics as a faculty member.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you, sir. For our introductory question, did you ever experience eating cuisine or food for an international flight? Particularly via a legacy air carrier, or airline, and particularly on economy class?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** Okay, thank you. So, how many long-haul flights per year have you experienced or international flights in that manner during the post-pandemic period?
- **Interviewee:** Twice a year.
- **Interviewer:** Okay, so two flights per year? So, international flights?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah.
- **Interviewer:** Not domestic?
- **Interviewee:** Does it include connecting flights?
- **Interviewer:** Yes, it can. Just as long as it is international, outside of the country.
- **Interviewee:** Yeah.
- **Interviewer:** May I, if so, may I ask which airline was it?
- **Interviewee:** It's Etihad, KLM, and Air France.
- **Interviewer:** Okay.
- **Interviewee:** So far.
- **Interviewer:** So far. With that said, we're about to ask a few questions about that, your experience. So, starting out with question number one, during your long-haul flight, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, it's significant because whatever food or whatever yeah, whatever food, the airline offers affects the mood of the customers so if they will be providing a quality food, then of course, we'll be happy during the flight.
- **Interviewer:** So it is an up side, particularly in your long-haul flights that you have experienced.
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** So, question number two. Is the provision or giving of in-flight food services being included as part of your ticket, including as a booking, an appealing factor to purchase that particular ticket. If so, what are these provisions that included in that ticket particularly for food service?

- **Interviewee:** Umm... well they provide us with of course lots of options so if you want vegan food or vegetarian food then uhh... they uhh offer that option so uhh... when I was flying Etihad of course uhh... since I'm a muslim its much better because they provided halal options as well, and the food when your flying to the middle east is mostly halal especially if you are flying with uhh... an Arab state-own airline.
- **Interviewer:** So it ahh... it does appeal to you that the food included, is it included?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, specially if they provide any pre-planned meals and the options that are available during the flight that schedule of flight.
- **Interviewer:** So with that it is connected with our third question particularly, how can you say that you are satisfied with the variety of food options being available variety of the airline?
- **Interviewee:** Well, I'm satisfied if there are lots of options. Of course there's a lot of options and a lot of variety so you can uhm... explore as well different types of foods that will be provided by that specific airline.
- **Interviewer:** Oh, that's good, so in your opinion uhh... with regards to the quality of the food that is being served to you, the cuisine we say, uhh... how important is it for you.. for your overall airline experience for that particular airline, why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... I'm sorry can you repeat?
- **Interviewer:** About this question uhh... it is a more general question it states that uhh... how... how important is it for the food to be given to you as an experience from the airline itself?
- **Interviewee:** You're asking how important?
- **Interviewer:** How important for the experience itself, that the food is being given to you by the airline?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... it usually comes with the *ano kasi* (what because of) the plane ticket, right? So uhh... it's highly favorable for me because uhh... I don't need to think of what to eat, I mean buy food at the terminals before boarding so it's uhm... it's highly favorable I mean, yeah it's good.
- **Interviewer:** So basically it's more efficient?
- **Interviewee:** Yeah, it's more efficient. It's not time consuming and it's uhh... more comfortable to fly knowing that you already have your food prepared by the airline so.
- **Interviewer:** So with that how does your experience with that food quality influence your intention to fly again with that airline, particularly they give good quality food and as you said the variety itself?
- **Interviewee:** Well it's uhm... it's it provides uhh... the quality of the airline if they provide quality food especially it's food then it will be uhm... it will become their you know remarkable [caters] remarkable it will become remarkable experience for the customers and will surely uhm... remember the airline by their food which is uhm... ahh... which is good for the airline of course since they will be remembered as the airline which provide quality food. So of course, if you'll be flying again, uhm... it's gonna be one to consider, the quality of the food.
- **Interviewer:** Particularly with that international flights?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, particularly with that international flight.
- **Interviewer:** So, considering that the quality of in flight is typically translates to more expensive tickets we may say, so how does this influence your choice in selecting the airline?

- **Interviewee:** Tsk, well for me, it doesn't really matter [the price], especially if it will provide me happiness you know. Good food is happiness and if you're happy, then you're satisfied, and uhm... actually I admit that comfortability or happiness is really expensive. So uhm... if you really want quality food then so you can pay for it because you know that experience would be worth the price and the food is worth the price.
- **Interviewer:** That's a good answer so, here is our last question uhh... how does the cultural appropriateness of the in-flight food and its quality influence your perception of the food quality and overall satisfaction with that particular airline?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... well uhh... it's actually uhh... exciting because uhm... for example, if you'll be flying to the Middle East, they'll be providing you uhm... some of the Mediterranean cuisine uhm... you know maybe food from that specific region so you can select that type of food uhm... but you know there are other options as well if you don't like that food so the thing is you have the choice actually have a taste their culture before actually getting to that place. So, it's for me, it's a big factor and it's a big plus points to that airlines to actually provide that option.
- **Interviewer:** So, it elevates your satisfaction?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, of course.
- **Interviewer:** So that will be all the questions uhh... here posted here so if you may say something additional about how cuisine influence your airline experience as a whole?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... well uhm... my only comment to that is that it is really a big factor because again, as I've mentioned a while ago, uhm... if the airline will provide bad food, it will leave a bad taste to the people and it will leave a bad experience as well. So, as we know uhh... people review a lot. They read reviews as well so it will be affecting their uhh... you know choices if the- to fly with that airline. So yeah.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you for that statement sir, thank you for uhh... being a respondent for our interview and hope you have a better.. great day today.
- **Interviewee:** A better day [laughs], a better life [laughs].
- **Interviewer:** That would be all. Thank you sir.
- **Interviewee:** Okay, welcome.

Informant 5 (Working Professional)
Passenger aboard a Flight (In-flight Food Cuisine)
Researcher/s: John Roy P. De Dios & Christian James N. Nilo

- **Interviewer:** Uhh... good afternoon sir, thank you for joining us today. But first can you please introduce yourself, state your name followed by age and occupation.
- **Interviewee:** Ah, yes uhh... my name is Engineer Jonathan Dela Peña. Uhh... I'm twenty-nine years old and I'm currently working as an instructor at PATTS College of Aeronautics.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you sir. For our introductory question, did you ever experience eating cuisine or food for an international flight via legacy airline, specifically economy class?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes I have. Uhh... specifically I have flown with Malaysian Airlines, Royal Brunei Airlines, and Philippine Airlines.
- **Interviewer:** Okay thank you. How many long-haul flights per year have you experienced during the post pandemic period? Is it two flights per year? three flights or more than that?
- **Interviewee:** Umm... well considering its a round trip flight, uhh... I will say twice a year.
- **Interviewer:** Okay, thank you thank you. If so, may I ask what airline it is?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... so recently I've flown with Royal Brunei Airlines from Brunei to Manila. Uhh... back and forth. Uhh... in twenty twenty-two (2022).
- **Interviewer:** Okay thank you. With that said, we are about to ask you a few questions regarding your experience. Question number one, during long-haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes definitely. For uhh- speaking of long-haul flights, okay so uhh... we are up in the air for hours or days okay so the food uhh quality really matters to the passengers. So uhh... if the food is good, the experience is great for the passengers.
- **Interviewer:** Okay thank you sir, moving to the second- wait. Uhh... so sir, uhh... you experienced that flight sir? Like an international flight uhh on a legacy airliner with the food quality sir?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** Would you say sir that it's significant?
- **Interviewee:** Yes. Uhh... it's significant.
- **Interviewer:** Hmm... why is it significant to you sir?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... well it's because umm... after tasting the food right, the- the- mem- the pa- ah, you know as a passenger right, I will look back uhh... at you know what we had right. So umm... another example- another reason is you know uhh... for- for the memories. For the memories of the experience. Ahh... aside from the quality of the food, we get to cherish the short time right uhh... we enjoyed the flight and usually its the important events are the- well first thing for me is the food.
- **Interviewer:** Ahh... okay so the food one of the most important parts of your flight sir?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** Ah, I see. Okay sir. Right moving on. Moving on, uhh... same question. Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase? If so, what are these provisions?

- **Interviewee:** Umm... yes ahh... so. it would be a really a matter of convenience versus uhh... experience. Okay so since I'm uhh... not a frequent flier, okay so the experience really matters most to me. Alright, so that experience uhh... one of them is the food, food experience.
- **Interviewer:** Aside from the food, are there any additions? Let's say an example, given utensils? Quality? So let's say either you get a plastic one or you get a metal one. What do you think uhh... any difference between the materials within- would play a factor in your satisfaction?
- **Interviewee:** Well in my opinion, the materials won't matter okay uhh... sometimes we had plastic, sometimes we had wooden utensils okay but I think they uhh... the business and the first class they will have uhh... higher quality utensils.
- **Interviewer:** Okay thank you, sir. Uhh... question three, how can you say that you are satisfied by the variety of options available on flights you've taken?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... the uhh... options- the variety uhh would really depend on the- the destination and arrival of the flight. Uhh... so, for example, uhh... flying with Royal Brunei Airlines uhh... we are only given uhh... two options uhh... for lunch okay umm... the first option was chicken marsala and the second option was uhh... pork stew- sorry uhm... beef stew because they don't serve uhh... pork in uhh... Brunei [laughs].
- **Interviewer:** Uhh... so sir, when it comes to the variety, would you say that those variety- like those uhh... selections of food that they provided to you, do you think it's satisfying to you?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes uhh... I get to try the food culture okay uhm... of the airlines so it's an unforgettable experience.
- **Interviewer:** Ah if I may ask sir, what do you think is more important? The quality of the food or the variety of the food? In an airline.
- **Interviewee:** Uhh in an airplane, I'd say the quality matters most than the variety.
- **Interviewer:** Ahh... I see thank you, sir. Uhh number four, in your opinion, with regards to the quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Ahh... yes uhh... so uhh... as I've uhm... explained uhh... before, right the uhh- it's a matter of getting to experience uhh... the food service umm... on an airplane. Okay so uhh... it's one of the unforgettable moments okay uhh... flying uhh... even to this day, I can still recall uhh... the food experience okay I had uhh... in the flight. Aside from that, I get to taste right uhh... to try their food culture uhh... of the airline.
- **Interviewer:** I see good. Uhh... question number five, how does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes so the intention here is that uhm... because I really like the food okay ahh... I would not only fly with them again, but I would also recommend uhh their- their service to others.
- **Interviewer:** I see sir so you would uhh... recommend the flight- uhh... the airline itself because of the food- of how great the food was?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes correct.
- **Interviewer:** I see. Okay. Six? Yeah. Six, considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline?
- **Interviewee:** Uhm... so I understand that uhm... all of the uhh... struggles of in-flight meals is the taste alright so in forty-thousand feet above the ground, uhh... our sense of taste uhh... would be impaired okay so I understand the additional cost right, that it takes to make the food delicious. Okay, so it would umm... be uhh... justified [laughs] okay in my opinion. The price of uhh... the ticket is okay with the food serving.

- **Interviewer:** I see so you would choose the more expensive ticket for the delicious experience of the in-flight cuisine?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, correct.
- **Interviewer:** I see. Uhh... last question, how does the cultural appropriateness of in-flight food and its quality influence customers' perception of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?
- **Interviewee:** Okay so in my opinion, uhm... the culture uhh... plays an important role uhh... in the variety and its what makes the airlines unique right uhh... unique right so uhh... for example when I've flown with Philippine Airlines, I still remember their Chicken Adobo right and when I've flown with Malaysian Airlines, I still remember their Nasi Lemak and then when I fly with uhh... Royal Brunei Airlines, I would always choose their Chicken Marsala. So, umm... to me, uhh... this really shows the richness of their culture, their food culture, and they want to share it with the uhh... passengers so this is really a great uhh... introduction window right, to tasting the- to experiencing the culture of the uhh... the airline's origin. Country of origin.
- **Interviewer:** So sir you are satisfied with how much culture they are providing you sir?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, correct.
- **Interviewer:** Ahh I see. Ah and also sir if I may ask, what again did they serve you on Malaysia Airlines?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh Nasi Lemak.
- **Interviewer:** Nasi Lemak. I see, I see. Okay that would be it. Yes actually. That would be it. Uhh that's all for this interview thank you sir, thank you for your time. Thank you very much sir.
- **Interviewee:** Good luck with your thesis [laughs].
- **Interviewer:** Thank you sir! Thank you!

Informant 6 (Working Professional)
Passengers aboard a Flight (In-flight Food Cuisine)
Researcher/s: John Roy P. De Dios & Christian James N. Nilo

- **Interviewer:** Good afternoon, thank you for joining us today. But first can you please introduce yourself? State your name followed by your age and occupation.
- **Interviewee:** Uhh.. my name is Nigel Hidalgo I'm twenty-eight- sorry turning twenty-nine. I'm a college instructor at PATTS College of Aeronautics.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you, sir, for our introductory question, did you ever experience eating cuisine or food for an international flight via legacy airliner, economy class?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes I've- I experienced both economy and business class.
- **Interviewer:** Okay, how many long-haul flights per year have you experienced during the post-pandemic period? Is it two flights per year, or is it three flights or more than that?
- **Interviewee:** Umm... more than that but for the long haul only one.
- **Interviewer:** Hmm... if so may I ask what airline is it?
- **Interviewee:** Ah, it was Cathay Pacific.
- **Interviewer:** Cathay Pacific, economy class sir?
- **Interviewee:** Both. Going business class, *pabalik ng* (going back to) Philippines it was economy.
- **Interviewer:** Okay thank you. With that said, we are about to ask you a few questions regarding your experience. Question number one, during long-haul flights, do you think that quality cuisine is significant to a better flight experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** Ah, for me it is important *kasi* (because) while you're stuck in the air, you're left with only, if ever there is in-flight entertainment and of course the food. And as a *foodie* (food-lover) I'd like really good food, appetizing and you know, good to look at.
- **Interviewer:** I see. Moving on to question two. Is the provision of in-flight food services being included as a part of the ticket an appealing factor to purchase? If so, what are these provisions?
- **Interviewee:** *Anong* (what) provisions?
- **Interviewer:** Provisions as in additional or let's say utensils. Instead of uhh... paper, and plastic, they use metal. So presentation.
- **Interviewee:** Ahh *siguro* (maybe) it's not a big factor if uhh... I guess for me because I'm not really particular but as expected with legacy airlines, it's usually *ano-* (what-) not paper cups and plastic- it's usually *ano-* (what-) their own utensils with their names so it's already included.
- **Interviewer:** I see uhh... sir what about sir uhh lets say uhh do you think its appealing lets say economy class but they include more than just the meal? Let's say there's meal but then there is also snacks and fruits, is that appealing to you?
- **Interviewee:** Ahh... yes that's very appealing.
- **Interviewer:** Why so sir?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... *kasi yun nga* (that's because) like I- uhh... during my flight before with CX or Cathay, it was long-haul so I've differentiated it from business to economy *kasi* going there I was business, if they serve- *sa* (on) business they will serve you *para siyang ano-* (it's like what-) five star ahh- by course *siya nabilang ko yun siguro parang* (I counted that maybe it's like) seven course *yun* (that's it) so *pag busog ka na* (when you are full), I think *lalagyan pa nila ng* (they will still add) food but *sa* (on) economy

nakalagay na siya sa isang (it was served by one) tray, although *medyo* (somewhat) similar *siya* (it's similar) but *yung sa* (on the economy *mas maunti* (quite little) and I think *mas* less (lesser) gourmet with less quality.

- **Interviewer:** I see sir pero (but) sir the economy class uhh... food, is it still like high standards sir? Is it still pretty good to you sir?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh it's still pretty good with CX *naman* (likewise) it's good. In other airlines, I don't wanna but it's not [laughs].
- **Interviewer:** Ah, I see sir so the quality is not really that compromised sir sa (on) economy class?
- **Interviewee:** *Oo* (Yes) not that compromised.
- **Interviewer:** I see, I see sir. Moving on to question three, how can you say that you are satisfied with the variety of options available on flights you've taken?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... *siguro* (maybe) I would say I'm satisfied- first of all if I'm not that hungry *na* (already) and second, *hindi mainit ulo ko* (I'm not hot-headed anymore). *Kasi* (Because) I've experienced before *sa ibang* (other) airline, although its business, but *yung binigay nila na* food (the food they serve in it) is not very nice and *yung sinerve nila na* ice cream (the ice cream that they serve) is melted *na* (already) so you know imagine after, *init yung ulo mo* (you'll be hot-headed).
- **Interviewer:** Have you had a similar experience with economy class?
- **Interviewee:** Ahh economy *naman*, *sa* economy *kasi* (for economy) they don't serve your desserts, just the food itself. Although *malaki* ang difference *niya* (there's a huge difference) I think it's also good quality *naman* (likewise).
- **Interviewer:** Sir in economy class, may I ask sir, in economy class, uhh... let's say the variety of food sir is it satisfying to you sir? In economy class. Ahh... variety like *yung mga* (those) options *niyo po* (your options) sir.
- **Interviewee:** Hmm... *sa* economy *kasi* (on economy class like) you don't have any options. *Sa* (on) business class they will hand you a card then you're gonna choose there. Second, I mean they don't really do that. Based on my *ano* (what) ha, my recent trip, they just put it out to you, and then yeah. That's it.
- **Interviewer:** I see. But sir it's still good quality?
- **Interviewee:** Its good quality *naman* (likewise).
- **Interviewer:** Okay. Question four. In your opinion with regards to quality of in-flight cuisine, how important is it for your airline experience? Why or why not?
- **Interviewee:** *May scale ba yun* (Is there a scale)? Like *halimbawa* (for example) on a scale of one to ten, *siguro* (maybe) I would say it would be a nine? A nine-point-five (9.5). Food is important to me *kasi ano-* (because it's-) I'm hypoglycemic so I have to have food *lagi* (always) although *kahit konti lang dapat* (even a little) I should eat and eat and of course *dapat* (it should be) nutritious and *hindi lang basta ano-* (it's not just like that) so yeah ayun (there). That's important.
- **Interviewer:** So, it's important to you sir because of your health sir?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, yes.
- **Interviewer:** But let's say it's also important because of course it's delicious?
- **Interviewee:** Yes, it's delicious.
- **Interviewer:** Must be very uhh appetizing.
- **Interviewee:** Yes appetizing.

- **Interviewer:** It's important to your airline comfort sir?
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** So, with that said your nine out of ten translates to comfort-
- **Interviewee:** Yes.
- **Interviewer:** And health?
- **Interviewee:** And health.
- **Interviewer:** Of course, thank you. Uhh... five, how does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?
- **Interviewee:** Hmm... sorry pakiulit?
- **Interviewer:** How does your experience with in-flight food quality influence your intention to fly again with the same airline?
- **Interviewee:** *Siguro* (Maybe) if the food is really good, I would not only fly with it again, I would also recommend it to my friends and I would continue to fly with them until *halimbawa maumay na ako* (for example I'm fed up), I get tired of it. Then I will switch to other airlines. You know, considering the route *halimbawa* (for example) uhh... *masarap nga yung food doon* (the food there is delicious) and my intended route is not there then I will not fly with that airline. But yes, food is a big uhh... big factor to me.
- **Interviewer:** So, let's say sir two airlines, and let's say airline A and airline B. And airline A's food is better, would you pick it?
- **Interviewee:** Hmm... yes, I would pick it.
- **Interviewer:** Thank you. Moving on to six. Considering that quality in-flight cuisine typically translates to a more expensive ticket, how does it influence your choice in selecting an airline?
- **Interviewee:** Hmm... *siguro* (maybe) like what I said before uhh... the food is really good you know uhh... *hindi naman ako madaling i-please sa* (I'm not easy to please with) food but *meron talagang* (there are) airlines *na tumatatak sa akin* (that would remind me) so I would continue to fly with that airlines. Especially you know *kung minsan kasi ibang* (sometimes different) route, *iba-iba sila ng* (they have different) cuisine *kasi iba-iba din ang* (because they have different) food selection so normally uhh... I would choose the type of destination I want *din- minsan* (like- sometimes) ha, I'd choose that type of destination I want based on what they would serve *sa* (on) aircraft. So for example, I'm gonna go to Japan. So usually they serve there *yung mga* foods *ng* Japanese cuisine (foods of Japanese cuisine), *ganun, ganun* (like that, like that). But if you're gonna go to Dubai, they're gonna serve you like *mga* (those) halal foods, *kung ano yung* (what's that) food *dun sa* (from the) destination *na pupuntahan ko* (where I'll be going). So *ayun* (there). Big factor.
- **Interviewer:** I see. Question number six, considering that quality in-flight cuisine- you already said that. seven *na* (already). Sorry, sorry so question seven. How does the cultural appropriateness of in-flight food and its quality influence customers' perceptions of food quality and overall satisfaction with the airline?
- **Interviewee:** Ahh... *so para siyang* (it's like) uhh... inclusivity *ganon* (like that)?
- **Interviewer:** Inclusivity, presentation, and let's say the effort they put in what they serve you in terms of, let's say Emirates-
- **Interviewee:** Ahh... okay okay *ako kasi* (because I am) uhh... *so sabi ko nga di ako mapili sa* (I'm not a picky at) food but my friends who I travel with *lagi* (always), they're very picky. So, one of them is vegan, he's on a vegan diet. Eh, *si CX, si Cathay meron silang* (it has) uhh... vegan friendly meal *pag mag t-travel ka ng* (if you will travel on) business *kasi p-pick mo lang yun* (because you'll pick that) prior to flight. *Parang* (Maybe) seventy-two hours before your flight. So, *sa kanya* (for him), based *sa* (on) experience *nakausap ko siya sabi niya* (when I talked to him he said), "*si CX is one of the airlines na ganun*" (it's like that) type of variety *na* (on) food. *Na sa* menu (It's in the menu) they have vegan friendly, they have vegetarian, they have low carb" *bla bla*

ganun, ganun (like that, like that). So I guess that's one good reason for *ano* (what) inclusivity or cultural appropriation- *tama ba* (is that correct)?

- **Interviewer:** Uhh... what about you sir? Like you appreciate their cultural appropriateness when it comes to them serving their cultural food to you?
- **Interviewee:** Ahh... yes yes I do especially if *ano- halimbawa* (what- for example) if I go to an exotic country uhh... I always do *kasi kapag pumunta ako ng* (because if I'm going to) exotic country *lagi ako bumibili ng* (I always buy) coffee so *yung mga* cabin crews (the cabin crews) *tinatanong ko sa kanila* (I'm asking them) where is the best coffee in Dubai *ganun, ganun tas sasabihin nila* (like that, like that and then they will say) we have here *lagi sila nag s-serve ng* coffee (they always serve coffee) so *ayun* (there) everytime *na tumatak yan sa akin* (it always remind me of that) everytime *may* (there's) flight, *nag a-ask ako ng* (I will ask) coffee *sa* (on) in-flight *kung meron sila* (if they have). *Tas tatanong ko kung saan galing* (Then I'll ask where's it come from) then *tatanong ko kung saan nabibili yun* (I'll ask where can I buy it) or *saang* (where) catering *nabibili yun* (can I buy) and you know *parang* (like) sharing of information.
- **Interviewer:** Uhh... sir what about sir in economy class? Like do they also show that culture sir? Like let's say- like what you said sir it depends *sa* (on) destination, *yung* (the) economy class do they also provide that cultural appropriateness?
- **Interviewee:** Uhh... yes *nung pumunta ako ng* (when I travelled to) Dubai- *kasi pabalik kami* (because going back) economy, so *ang laki talaga ng* (there's a huge) difference *na napansin ko kasi yung* (because I realized that) business class *papunta doon* (going there), they will serve you coffee *na talaga maganda yung* (it has a good) presentation, *masarap yung lasa* (the taste is good), *nung pauwi na kami sa* (when we're going home) economy, *masarap din naman* (likewise it taste good). *Hindi siya ganun kasarap sa* (It's not like that delicious in) business *tas sinerve siya naka paper cup lang* (the serving is like only on a paper cup) [laughs]. *Tas ayun okay lang naman* (But then again, it's still okay) since its economy *pero* (but) paper cup *tapos merong tatak ng* (then it has a logo of the) airline.
- **Interviewer:** Sir, is it the same coffee?
- **Interviewee:** *Parang hindi* (I think it's not) [laughs].
- **Interviewer:** *Parang hindi* (It's not) sir?
- **Interviewee:** *Mas lower, masarap pero medyo* (it's good but like) lower class *ng onti* (a bit).
- **Interviewer:** So, sir when it comes to economy class, still sir comparing like the economy class to- economy class with food and economy class without food. Uhh... what would you prefer, sir?
- **Interviewee:** Economy class with food or without food?
- **Interviewer:** Yes, sir what would you prefer sir?
- **Interviewee:** With food [laughs].
- **Interviewer:** Ah, it really enhances your experience sir?
- **Interviewee:** *Oo, oo kasi diba pag low cost* (Yes, yes because it's like if it's low cost), *walang* (there's no) food?
- **Interviewer:** Yes, *po* sir.
- **Interviewee:** *Ayun* (There) yeah. I think uhh... *eto pala kasi* (here it's like because) my sister she works *sa* (on) low cost airline so *yung* (the) food uhh... *yung mga* (the) crew meal *na binebenta nila* (they sell) usually *ang* (the) food *wala siyang lasa tas napansin ko yung* (there's no taste then I noticed the) bag *ng* sister *ko* (the bag of my sister) *may iba't ibang klasing* (there are different) condiments. *Sabi ko, para saan yan?* (I said, what's the purpose of those?) *Sabi niya, para sa* food *daw* (She said, it's for the food) *kasi ibang-* (because other-) *yung ibang* passengers (other passengers) *doon nag r-reklamo walang lasa yung* food (they are complaining about the food is tasteless) so *binibigyan niya lang daw niya* (she's giving it).

- **Interviewer:** I see, I see.
- **Interviewee:** Sorry *medyo* (a little) [laughs] trivia.
- **Interviewer:** [laughs] It's okay sir. So, sir like *kahit- pero* (like- but) sir, *yung* (the) legacy airliners and economy class, *may lasa naman po yung pagkain* (is there any taste in the food)?
- **Interviewee:** *May lasa naman yung* food (The food has a taste) like *sa* (on) PAL *ayun* (there). Yeah.
- **Interviewee:** Okay that's it sir. Okay I think that's it, thank you sir thank you for your time.
- **Interviewer:** Good luck guys good luck, let me know how it goes.
- **Interviewee:** Hopefully it goes well. [laughs] yeah.

APPENDIX F: PLAGIARISM CHECK

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APPENDIX G: BIONOTE

Jofranz L. Amodia, a 22-year-old, B.S. Air Transportation student. Born from Pasay City, Metro Manila. His educational journey began and flourished at Santa Clara Parish School, where he completed both Junior High School and Senior High School. Driven by his passion for aviation and a deep-seated love for his country, Jofranz aspires to fulfill his dream of becoming a pilot or serving in the Philippines Air Force. His formative years were enriched by various work experiences, including roles in the retail shoes business and the middleman between the lessee and lessor of boarding houses in Pasay City and Quezon City, reflecting his industrious spirit and adaptability. He is determined to set his sights on a goal, and he relentlessly pursues it. Armed with strong interpersonal skills and a fearless attitude toward new challenges, he embodies resilience and a readiness to embrace opportunities.

John Roy P. De Dios, a 21-year old, a B.S. Air Transportation student. Born in Pasay City, Metro Manila, he resided there for 17 years before moving to Parañaque City where he is also currently pursuing his education. He finished both his primary and secondary education in the Sacred Heart School in Parañaque City before enrolling in PATTS College of Aeronautics in 2019 where he finished Senior High School in 2021. With regards to his aspirations in life, he never really had a specific goal aside from that of financial independence and a secure career. With that in mind, he made the decision to pursue a career in aviation as he viewed it as the most optimal career, he could pour his efforts and hard work towards. With that said, he is an individual dedicated to this cause and is willing to sacrifice a devotion of blood, sweat, and tears to this endeavor of not only a brighter future but also of finding oneself and his purpose in life. With his set of skills and eagerness to learn and adapt to the ever- changing landscape of aviation and the Philippines itself, he is prepared to give his heart and soul to manifest destiny, his dreams, and ambitions in life.

Christian James N. Nilo, a 21-year-old, B.S. Air Transportation student studying at PATTS College of Aeronautics. Born in Cavite City and was subsequently raised in Dubai, United Arab Emirates. It was with his first international flight that sparked his curiosity and passion for aviation. He studied in The Philippine School, Dubai for the majority of his school life until he decided to return in the Philippines where he studied at FEU Diliman to finish his Senior High School. After which he graduated and currently stands in PATTS College of Aeronautics, where he will do what it takes to achieve his career goal. His enthusiasm and passion for aviation is what fuels his motivation and determination to become a pilot or a professional aviation personnel. His sheer will and resolution may put him right in the field of aviation or even in the cockpit of his dreams. He understands failure and always strives to be better and to adapt in any situation that is handed to him. Pursuing his dreams, he vows to ensure his part in society would be stagnant and acts to impart his skills in the aviation world of the Philippines.

Andrei Bea D. Nuñez, a 21-year-old, B.S. Air Transportation student. Born in Quezon City, Metro Manila, embodying profound dedication and passion for aviation industry. Beginning her journey at PATTS in 2019, she transitioned seamlessly from De La Salle Araneta University's Junior High School, where she excelled both academically and as a Taekwondo athlete. In 2019, Bea's group project, "A Comparative Study between the Vermiculture of European Nightcrawler (*Eisenia Hortensis*) and Blue worms (*Perionyx Excavates*) in hydroponics to support urban gardening," earned accolades as the second-best investigatory project at DLSAU's Research Congress. This achievement highlights her diverse talents and commitment to sustainable practices alongside her aviation aspirations. With unwavering courage and a relentless drive for excellence, Bea is determined to fulfill her ambition of becoming a successful pilot. Her active role as a student-leader at PATTS College of Aeronautics underscores her readiness to contribute significantly to the aviation industry, making her a promising figure in the field.

Rose Anne A. Pocong, a 21-year-old, currently taking a course of B.S. Air Transportation student. Born in Manila and now resides in Bacoor City, Cavite. She completed her elementary education at Escuela La Madrid of Cavite, junior high school at St. Michael's Institute and graduated senior high school at Manila Tytana Colleges. She never had a specific dream in life because of how simple yet talented and hardworking she is when it comes to artistic and practical skills. Even though she is an introvert person at first, she is always curious about trying things that might help her realize what she wanted to pursue in life, leading to that curiosity of trying to be part of the field in aviation. From that moment, she is now dedicated to learning about technical stuff that involves aircraft and flying, hoping that someday, she will be able to help those who are afraid to try and discover something new in life and become a pilot or any occupation that involves the industry of aviation in the future. May her determination and commitment guide her with aspiration in herself. Along with hope and positivity, she will be able to share and apply all the learning experiences she has with everyone, even the simplest thing, matters.

Amadeus Euclid Poliran, a 20-year-old, B.S. Air Transportation student. Born in Quezon City and was raised in Taguig City, Metro Manila. He completed his Senior High School education at Bloomfield Academy of Makati and his Junior High School at Maranatha Christian Academy. Amadeus is passionately dedicated to realizing his dream of becoming a pilot, driven by a strong vision for the future of aviation. His goal is to contribute to the efficiency, innovation, and safety of flight operations within a reputable airline, aiming to make a significant impact on the aviation industry. His commitment and forward-thinking approach reflect his determination to excel in his chosen field, embodying a profound aspiration to elevate standards and achieve excellence in aviation.

Emanuel M. Ticsay, a 21-year-old B.S. Air Transportation student. From Quezon City, Metro Manila, he grew up in the said city where he found his passion for aviation. He studied as a Junior High School student at St. Joseph's College of Quezon City before pursuing his aviation course at PATTS College of Aeronautics in 2019. He completed his Senior High School with honors in 2021. His passion for aviation has brought him to have a goal of being a part of this field with a goal of becoming a pilot or becoming an air traffic controller. With this passion and goals, he strives to do the best he can to achieve this goal showing his unwavering will to attain his aspirations. With his perseverance to achieve goals, he will contribute to this strive to innovate and create a more resilient aviation industry in the country paving the way for a more prosperous aviation scene in the Philippines with the knowledge that he has learnt through the years.